

SEISMEC

Supporting European Industry Success Maximization
through Empowerment Centred development

D1.1

Benchmarking of concepts and
dimensions of human-centrism

Transilvania IT

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Abstract

Human-centrism is a critical concept that is more and more important across all European industries and various domains, including technology, design, and policy. This benchmark study explores the dimensions and underlying concepts of human-centrism. By analyzing existing literature and case studies, we identify key elements such as user needs, ethical considerations, and inclusivity. Our findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how to create more human-centric industries and services.

Keywords

Human-centric, Industry 5.0, CAPS framework, Benchmarking

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Acronyms and definitions

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action
CAPS	Creativity + Collaboration/ Autonomy + Automation/ Privacy + Productivity/ Safety + Security
EU	European Union
IoT	Internet of Things
IT&C	Information Technology and Communication
MHC	Meaningful Human Control
ML	Machine Learning
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise

1 Executive summary

Along with sustainability and resilience, human-centrism is one of the core principles related to the emerging concept of Industry 5.0. It is the successor of Industry 4.0, aiming to replace the tech-driven forces of the previous industrial strategies within the European Union (EU) that were under the Industry 4.0 umbrella. Since SEISMEC focuses on bridging the tensions between economic competitiveness and worker empowerment, the analysis of human-centrism approaches is paramount to providing a foundation for the project. To measure the transition to human-centric workplaces, we envision four empowerment factors that play a significant role: Collaboration – Creativity, Autonomy-Automation, Privacy-Productivity, Safety – Job Satisfaction (CAPS).

The aim of this deliverable is to identify existing practices and offer defining guidelines regarding human-centrism. The research will do so by looking at human-centrism through mixed methods. First, we look into existing practices related to human-centrism from past and on-going European projects to identify the various vantage points of human-centrism. Secondly, we introduce and define the CAPS factors. Thirdly, we provide an overview on on-going discussions and connections between the main concepts of the project – Industry 5.0, human-centrism, and the CAPS factors. Lastly, we developed a practical initial assessment of human-centric practices at employee, organisation, and industry levels based on the CAPS empowerment factors.

2 Introduction

When discussing about the future of work and the overall discourse on the impact of technology in the workplace, there is no doubt that the modern workplace is changing. Not only due to digital transformation, but also because of the changes brought about by the pandemic in terms of work flexibilization, for instance. Policy discussions have evolved from a “techno-centric” perspective to a “human-centric” perspective within the move towards Industry 5.0, focused on sustainability, resilience, and human-centrism (European Commission, 2021). This shift does not come at the expense of technology integration, which requires many more efforts at the European level, as per the Digital Decade programme. Rather, societies must learn to mend this tension between economic competitiveness and worker empowerment. SEISMEC has embarked on this very journey, namely to pilot the shift towards human-centric industries.

This deliverable provides the starting point for this journey, as it aims to conceptualise human-centrism and to provide an initial instrument of assessment of human-centric workplaces. We do this by looking into several empowerment factors that can bridge the gap between worker empowerment and economic competitiveness, namely the CAPS factors - Collaboration - Creativity, Autonomy-Automation, Privacy-Productivity, Safety - Job Satisfaction. We contextualise human-centrism from a theoretical perspective by defining the CAPS empowerment factors and surveying the literature to identify and validate the connections between these concepts, Industry 5.0 and human-centrism. Additionally, we provide an empirical look into human-centrism by examining on-going and past European funded projects.

The structure of the deliverable proceeds as follows: first, we look into existing practices related to human-centrism from past and on-going European projects to identify the various vantage points of human-centrism. Secondly, we introduce and define the CAPS factors. Thirdly, we provide an overview on on-going discussions and connections between the main concepts of the project - Industry 5.0, human-centrism, and the CAPS factors. Finally, based on the

findings, we develop an initial benchmarking exercise for the assessment of human-centric practices in the workplace. For each of the CAPS empowerment factors, we designed a series of questions of self-reflection with regards to the human-centric quality of the practices, tools, procedures, activities, structures, and relations in which social partners engage at employee, organisation, and industry levels.

3 Empirical analysis of existing European projects tackling human-centrism

3.1 Introduction

Industry 5.0 rests on several pillars, namely resilience, sustainability and human-centrism. There have been a lot of theoretical and policy discussions with relation to resilience and sustainability, especially as regards pandemic preparedness and response and the twin transition. At the same time, human-centrism has been defined more as a differentiating factor against “techno-centrism”, which is the central pillar of Industry 4.0 (BEYOND 4.0, 2023, European Commission, 2021). The main question this section aims to answer is whether this is all there is. We do this by looking into past and on-going European projects to identify the practices of human-centrism in various industries (manufacturing, retail, human resources etc), countries and by engaging with different technologies (AI, robotics, AR/VR). This section proceeds as follows: first, we provide the methodological framework centered on a quantitative and qualitative analysis of human-centrism. Then, the document looks into practices and guidelines for human-centrism from previous and ongoing European projects. Finally, it provides a connection with the CAPS factors to identify connections between this framework and existing research investigations.

3.2 Methodology

The main research questions of this investigation are:

- How is human centrism applied in the current European industrial ecosystem (incl. previous and existing EU funded projects)?
- What are the factors (geographical, cultural, and ecosystem related factors) that influence diverging applications of the concept?

The research design proceeded as follows:

- The main point of data collection is the CORDIS database that includes European funded projects mainly within the Horizon scheme
- Several keywords were identified and used for the search and identification of projects relevant to the human-centrism concept: ‘human-centric’, ‘Industry 4.0’, ‘Industry 5.0’ and ‘human-centrism’
- The search was restricted to projects in the period from 2014 until 2023. The reason for this choice is that the concept of Industry 4.0 started in 2016, as a result of the German Industrie 4.0 strategy
- A qualitative analysis of the project objectives and main deliverables available on the CORDIS database was performed to eliminate projects that do not include the human factor in their research and innovation activities. Project deliverables and subsequent scientific articles are analysed to distil the human-centric approach from the objective of the project to the actual results. We aim to investigate What is human-centric research and development in these projects, behind the use of the buzzword?
- A quantitative analysis aiming to look at geographical and industrial representations was performed
- A tentative definition of human-centrism is provided at the beginning of the research, which is compared with the results of the empirical investigation in order to identify gaps in the existing practices

3.3 Empirical layer: Research results

Analysis of research results. Methodological note

A qualitative analysis of the project objectives and main deliverables available on the CORDIS database was performed to eliminate projects that do not include the human factor in their research and innovation activities.

The search in CORDIS was based on four keywords that yielded a total of 87 results, as follows:

- Industry 4.0 - 48 project results
- Industry 5.0 - 13 project results
- Human-centric - 24 project results
- Human-centrism - 2 project results

In order to guide the research and the elimination process as well, a tentative definition of human-centrism was used: **an approach to socio-economic activities that is rooted in the needs, experiences, perceptions and values of humans for the design, deployment and evaluation of technology.** This definition considers the socio-technical approach that forms the theoretical basis of SEISMEC. It serves as a baseline for research, and it will be refined as a result of the research activities.

Based on this definition, several projects were eliminated, especially because their outlook and investigation were more techno-centric than human-centric. In total, 22 projects remained for analysis that can provide insight into human-centrism. 2 projects - SURE 5.0 and Up-Skill were doubled in the count, as they were listed as search results both for 'Industry 4.0' and 'Industry 5.0'. The analysis then started from 20 Horizon projects that can provide insights into human-centrism.

Project deliverables and subsequent scientific articles were analysed to distil the human-centric approach from the project's objective to the actual results. The main question addressed here is: What is human-centric research and development in the projects behind the buzzword? Indeed, human-centrism can be perceived as a buzzword and not have any substance, considering its perceived significance, which is a lot of the time in contradiction with the traditional economic thinking rooted in productivity and competitiveness (Daron Acemoglu and Simon Johnson 2022).

Qualitative analysis

The framework for analysis looked at:

- the main concepts related to human-centrism from the projects

- the main perspectives of analysis: human/worker, business, technological, organisational, anthropological (ultimately integrated into the human/worker perspective)
- the connection between the main ideas, the SEISMEC core idea and the CAPS framework
- connections with the concepts of Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0 - as defined in the policy documents of the European Commission

Concepts present in the sample of analysis

What choice of concepts do the projects use to describe and include the human perspective in their research? There are a variety of conceptualisations regarding human-centrism, as follows:

- “Cooperative human-centric autonomy” - referring to the autonomy of the technology systems as human reactions are fed into the AI model to improve their functioning;
- human-centric systems - where the human “is both an element of the control system and a design criterion” (COMAN PROJECT);
- “Human-guided symbolic learning” - defined as a new paradigm for building AI systems for application in sectors where human agency/accountability is essential“ (TRUST-AI PROJECT);
- “Human-in-the-loop” scheme - referring to the inclusion of human feedback in the smart manufacturing systems (PERKS project)
- “Collaborative intelligence”, understood as the integration of human and artificial intelligence to accomplish tasks in the workplace;
- “Human-machine interaction” that leads to the paradigm of the new type of worker, entitled “Operator 4.0” (SME 4.0);
- “Human-robot collaboration”, manifested in the use of cobots, for instance;
- “The human factor”, understood as the specificities of humans in different workplace scenarios.
- “Human-in-the-loop”, understood as the active involvement of the humans in the development of AI systems

Despite their proclamation of being human-centric, not all these conceptualisations fit the bill. They are human-related, not necessarily human-centric, which is especially obvious in concepts, such as “human-machine interaction/collaboration” or human-in-the-loop“, which point to the integration of a human perspective in the development or implementation of technologies, but not starting with human needs and specificities. Indeed, the integration of the two is a prerequisite for Industry 5.0, but Industry 5.0 refers to much more than the complementarity between the ultimate goal of automation and the pursuit of the human perspective in the workplace alongside technology. This paradigm also refers to the protection of fundamental human rights in the process, integration of the needs of the worker, worker empowerment, identifying the right skills to fit the new economic models, etc. (Oeij, Dhondt, and Lenaerts 2023).

Perspectives of analysis of human-centrism

Several perspectives of analysis were identified from the project objectives, the declared thematics and the subjects of the use cases and pilots: human, business-oriented, technological, and organisational.

The technology behind the human-centric approach was the main unit of analysis in the identified projects. Although it might seem like a contradiction, the technological perspective regards the research, development and deployment of technologies that might implement the human-centric approach in several use cases and industries. 14 out of the 20 projects were technology-focused, with a specific focus on artificial intelligence (AI) for instance. **Explainable AI (xAI)**, robust AI, meaningful AI and distributed AI are just some examples that aim to illustrate the need to include the human perspective in technological research. In their research within the COMAN project, Tocchetti et al (2022) highlight the significant role of humans in training and evaluating robust AI systems, as they investigate the existing research on AI robustness (Tocchetti et al. 2022). They identify that the Machine Learning (ML) practitioner’s perspective is missing from the research on developing robust AI systems and that humans have significant untapped potential to identify errors in AI systems.

Meaningful AI is yet another concept detailed within the sample analysis that aims to develop a framework for human-centric technologies. MUHAI is the project whose aim is to develop AI technology “focusing on meaning and understanding” (CORDIS 2022). They define meaningful AI as technology that is sensitive to context and that can perform deliberative reasoning, as opposed to the current data-driven models that are only reactive (Luc Steels (ed.), n.d.). Understanding AI solutions refers to the integration of different perspectives derived from different sources of information (Luc Steels (ed.), n.d.).

Other technologies approached in the projects analysed that aim to build human-centric technologies are AR/VR, 6G connectivity, cybersecurity solutions or robotics. Nevertheless, the **vast majority of projects analysed related to applied research looking** more into the human-centric application of technologies in particular contexts. Particular use cases are also significant to understand the potential and challenges of human-centric technologies.

Technology applications in human-centric projects

The projects analysed look towards a variety of applications of technologies. Smart manufacturing is one of the main scenarios for the application of human-centric technologies, followed by mobility - autonomous driving, smart highways, healthcare or energy. Smart manufacturing is the quintessential application of Industry 4.0 concepts which aims for more efficient production using technologies, such as Digital Twins or AI, AR/VR or robotics. Examples of activities and integration of human/worker perspectives in these smart manufacturing projects include:

- development of a human-robot collaborative workstation
- development of job scheduling tools for factories to allow for more automation and less disturbances in the manufacturing process
- creation of a mixed model production line that integrates workers and robots to assemble distinct versions of a product on the same assembly line

Several other industries are present in the projects analysed, from the creative industries and tourism to aviation and aerospace, but the descriptions and/or actual applications published are scarce, either because the projects are new and/or currently under implementation, or because the reporting is not available yet.

Other examples that are mentioned are AI and/or AR/VR tools that help workers work better and in a more flexible manner, in the form of virtual coaches, job scheduling tools and even other tools, which help workers schedule their breaks in a more efficient manner so as to become more focused and increase job satisfaction. Hence, we can conclude that there are hard and soft tools developed within the projects aiming to make workplaces more human-centric. Soft tools - such as software - are developed and deployed to boost trust, flexibility and job satisfaction, while the hard tools - such as cobots - are deployed for productivity purposes.

The business perspective

The business perspective towards human-centrism manifests itself in several ways within the projects investigated. From a bird's-eye view, a vast majority of all the projects have a **business dimension**, considering that they aim to develop certain technologies, test approaches and solutions in a real world context, thus employing a case study approach in certain SMEs or companies. Zooming in, there are also a handful of projects (SME 5.0, SURE 5.0, BridgeSMEs) that focus entirely on building knowledge on adapting the business models of SMEs to be fit for Industry 5.0. Several industrial sectors are chosen for this endeavour:

- mobility, transport, automotive, aerospace, electronics (SURE 5.0)
- mobility, transport, automotive, aerospace and defence, electronic, cultural and creative industries, tourism (BridgeSMEs)

The Industry 5.0 focus is split in these projects, some looking towards providing tools and insight into introducing the other Industry 5.0 elements, namely

resilience and sustainability (the case with SURE 5.0 and EARASHI, for instance). In this case, sustainability is proposed as a differentiation factor for businesses.

Human-centrism is translated into **introducing ethical aspects** within SME strategic improvement plans or as a multi-faceted set of challenges that relate to a human-centric way of integrating smart devices into worker activities. SURE 5.0 documents point towards specific factors, such as “**acceptance by the people, ergonomics, hardware, legal aspects, safety and change management**” (SURE 5.0 2024). **Acceptance of technologies** is a key issue from a business perspective, since they involve further investments and expenses. Human-centrism as a key “to boost productivity, as well as health, safety and well-being” is yet another approach. **Here, the technological perspective is present as well, since the challenge for acceptance, as well as safety and other human-centric values present in the projects, is connected to assistive technologies such as exoskeletons or embodied AI (the case of EARASHI with use cases into monitoring workers’ stress levels or gamification to maintain the workplace attractive) (EARASHI 2023).**

Additionally, one significant aspect for Industry 5.0 adoption is the **training and preparedness of workers** from a business perspective (SURE 5.0 and SME 5.0).

Indeed, the business perspective focuses on the gains to productivity and competitiveness when implementing the principles of Industry 5.0 and human-centrism implicitly. PERKS developed digital tools for the improvement of procedural work, which translates into time saved and gains in efficiency. Here, the business perspective matches with the technology angles analysed in the previous section, which translate human-centrism as “human-in-the-loop”. The business and technology perspectives are intertwined, since the use of technology is constantly linked with gains in efficiency, productivity and revenues (Thatcher and Oliver 2001).

The section below develops the business perspective by looking into the various industries that are subject to the research in the projects.

Industrial perspectives

When looking at the distribution of use cases, pilots and industries where the human-centric perspective is analysed, the distribution is quite varied.

Figure 1 - Overview of the domains and use cases in European projects. Source: own elaboration based on CORDIS data

We can observe two spikes in the Figure 1 above, namely AI and Smart Manufacturing. They are the key items of the Industry 4.0 paradigm, which emphasises a technology-driven mindset for companies. Nevertheless, as the analysis above shows, there have been projects that have focused on developing a set of human-centric principles in smart manufacturing. There are also other projects that do focus on developing a HR perspective on the introduction of technology in the workplace, such as working with an aging workforce, developing skill sets for Industry 5.0, but HR is not the main focus domain in the projects analysed.

Pilot name/nr.	Ecosystem	Role	Size	Country	Advanced Technologies	Keywords / tools	Innovative dimensions						
							Work organisation (13.1)	Skills & training (13.2)	Health & safety (13.2)	Management & governance (13.3)	Business models (13.3)	Corporate values & ethics (13.3)	Tasks & functions (13.4)
1. Zagreb Airport	Aerospace	Inspection	Large	HR	AI, CC, HMI, IOT	AI anomaly detection			X				X
3. Arivia	Agrifood	Inspection	Large	EL	AI	AI anomaly detection		X					X
16. Fratelli Piacenza	Textile	Inspection	Large	IT	AI	AI anomaly detection				X			X
2. Kvalitetas	Agrifood	Flexible	SME	LT	AI, IOT, WES, TOS	AI fusion - Decision support					X		X
17. ARCTUR	Tourism	Service	SME	SI	AI, BD, MD	AI fusion - Decision support Forecasting	X	X		X	X		
4. Mostostal	Construction	Operator	Large	PL	AI, SIM	AI fusion - Decision support	X					X	
12. Thales	Civil Security	Rescuer	Large	FR	TOS, VR	Imaging with drones control interface for drones using VR helmets.		X	X				X
8. Atlas Copco	Energy intensive	Technician	Large	BE	AI, DA	Instruct service personnel	X	X					
11. Michelin	Automotive	Operator	Large	FR	AI, CC, MD	Instruct service personnel	X	X					
13. Go Tulip	Proximity	Driver	Start-up	NL	AI, CC, MD	Scheduling and route planning	X						
5. NS Web Development	Creative Industries (CCI)	Developer	SME	RS	AI, SN	HR - improving working environment	X	X					
6. NTT Data	Digital	Developer	Large	RO	SN	HR - improving working environment	X			X		X	
10. Buurtzorg	Health	Carer	SME	NL	AI, BD, CC, MD	HR - improving working environment	X			X	X		
18. Malt	Cross-sector	Flexible	SME	FR, DE, SP, NL, BE	AI, BD, CC, MD	HR - recruitment and selection	X			X	X	X	
7. Infineon	Electronics	Applicant	Large	AT	AI, HMI	Training and Interfaces		X					X
9. ATEs	Energy renewables	Technician	Large	TR	VR, SIM	Training		X	X				
14. iFarm & Farn Now	Retail & Agrifood	Farmer	Start-up	FL, AT	AI, AT, HMD, WD	Training and Monitoring		X	X				

Figure 2 - Overview of SEISMEC pilots based on ecosystems and industries. Source: SEISMEC application form

Otherwise, we can observe a variety of industrial sectors and ecosystems. How do these compare with the ecosystems that SEISMEC tackles? As we can see from Figure 2, the main technology that is being tackled is AI. When looking at domains, the picture is a bit different. SEISMEC tackles industries that are not present in the projects analysed, such as Construction, Agrifood, Textiles, Civil Security, Electronics. In this sense, we can argue that there is a concentration in the projects analysed compared to the SEISMEC project.

The worker/human perspective

The **worker/human perspective** is centred on a set of qualities: **human acceptance** of technology, **technology as an assistant** for particular worker categories, **human involvement** in the development of the technology, and work-life balance. The **skills focus in the human-centric workplace** is present in just a few projects (**BRIDGES 5.0**, for instance at a general level). However, most of the projects dealing with skills relate to them gaining skills for industries that might fit

the Industry 5.0 logic, such as circular manufacturing, green and digital skills or the energy sector (DENIM, DaCAPO etc).

As regards assistance and acceptance (EARASHI), these approaches focus on workers being the passive receivers of technology. Here, taking the human factor into account and human-machine interaction are examples of the visions of human-centrism (MAIA, for instance). Nevertheless, workers are involved in the **co-design and/or co-creation phases of the new technologies that are tested. Collaborative technologies are the main way in which the human-centric vision is manifested.**

Projects show that this boosts support and interest in working with such technologies, such as virtual coaches or flexible job scheduling tools for a greater **work-life balance**. Intrapreneurship is yet another example of a means towards worker empowerment. On the flip side, regardless of the workers' involvement, ethics and privacy issues arise when working with the designed technologies.

Age is yet another component that is analysed, but only in a few projects (AGING@WORK, SME 4.0). In this sense, human centrism is a challenge for older workers, while it is a differentiation factor that might attract younger generations. The approach of older workers is particularly challenging, since it is a specific issue for the European economy affected by aging and lower natality.

As regards the direct focus on workers versus technology, the perspective is quite split, even in the projects that entail activities involving workers or looking at ways to build human-centric technology.

One particular perspective that is correlated with the human perspective takes a critical perspective on the development of technology. **We call it the anthropological perspective**, developed within DCODE. Contestation of the current discourses towards technology is at the core of the research. Stakeholder integration, creating contexts to talk about technology, different imaginaries regarding AI, and the active contestation of “innovation for the sake of motivation”, are some of the main messages that point towards truly

integrating the human perspective in technological development (Collins and Redström 2022).

Organisational perspective

The organisational perspective refers to discussions, questions and investigations into the division of labour that define how work is organised (Oeij 2024). The projects investigated tend to focus more on the acquisition of skills and developing technologies than looking into exactly how the organisation of work is centred on humans' needs. In this sense, the organisational focus is not high. Nevertheless, there are some references to work organisations in some of the projects investigated. For instance, the Up-skill project tackles and identifies the work organisation perspective as significant for the adaptation of companies to Industry 5.0, according to the literature surveyed in the project, but the project still focuses on skills and training (UpSkill 2023). Another example is the Bridges 5.0 project, which does take an organisational perspective indirectly by looking at the skills necessary for the two actors in the division of labour - management and employees - to build towards Industry 5.0 companies.

There is a generalised acknowledgement that Industry 5.0 is still an undefined concept and that human-centric practices are not yet crystallised. In this sense, the organisational perspective remains underdeveloped since several projects mention this gap in knowledge. For instance, Beyond 4.0 starts also from the acknowledgement that “companies do not yet know what Industry 5.0 involves in terms of workplace practices and investments” and highlights the importance of thinking not only about acquiring skills for the new context, but also “regarding new technology’s introduction and implementation as a social process both for workers and other stakeholders” (BEYOND 4.0 2023, 5).

Geographical perspectives

SEISMEC aims to cover the diversity of the European industrial landscape. The outlook towards the previous European-funded projects looking into human-centrism shows that human-centrism is touched upon by a variety of industries

and countries. Hence, showcasing the geographical diversity is also paramount to understanding human-centrism, but also to identifying certain gaps that are to be addressed in the SEISMEC projects and pilots.

To provide a geographical outlook and offer clarity, we looked at the countries of the main applicants in the 20 projects that are under analysis. The results are showcased in the following map:

Figure 3 - Map of the geographical distribution of European projects dealing with human-centrism. Source of data: CORDIS, authors' own composition

Out of the 21 projects, **Italy** is the leader, with a number of 8 projects run by main applications coming from this country, followed by a relatively equal distribution between countries from Western Europe. **Greece** stands out as being the only Eastern country (when looking at a complete East-West division in the EU) with projects looking into human-centric technologies.

Connection with CAPS

An overview of the projects analysed shows that the research developed focuses on such factors as trade-offs rather than complementary approaches. For instance, **productivity and efficiency of companies are the key targets of digitalisation and several projects target the use of technologies for improving productivity of workers** (ZDMP, TRUST-AI and SME 4.0 with its mixed model production example). Nevertheless, some projects look at productivity from other angles, such as EARASHI, which sees human-centrism as a key to productivity (EARASHI 2023). D-CODE tackles privacy and productivity, considering data “to be at the nexus of both of them” (Avlona 2022), but it sees it as “**Privacy versus Productivity**” instead of looking into ways to overcome this tension. On the other hand, privacy is a value strongly regarded by workers and several projects highlight it as a challenge and as a prerequisite for the development and adoption of technologies in the workplace (TEACHING). Additionally, it is closely tied to the technological devices that monitor their activities. Wearables are examples of devices that might cause concern for workers (EARASHI). Moreover, privacy is also a concern not only for the use of technology (AGINNG@WORK), but also for the collection and exploitation of data (EARASHI, D-CODE).

Automation is present in virtually all the projects analysed, as is obvious also in the short industrial analysis below. Typically, automation is a core characteristic of Industry 4.0 and results in a techno-centric approach towards organisation, but the projects do aim to transcend this view, with a few exceptions (SME 4.0). Several projects aim to balance it with approaches, such as human-in-the-loop (PERKS, EARASHI), the human factor (MAIA) and co-creation principles. On the other hand, the presence of **autonomy is twofold: autonomy of the systems developed and autonomy of the human, respectively**. The former is connected to Industry 4.0 principles and it is connected with the qualifier “trustworthy” in order to showcase a rapprochement towards a human-centric approach (EARASHI, DEDICAT6G, TRUST-AI). The TEACHING project is the main illustrator of this idea, with the aim of developing a “human-centred cyber-physical system for autonomous safety-critical tasks.” This system was designed to be used for autonomous driving and the project imagines a “cooperative human-centric

autonomy” where real time human reactions are fed into an AI model to adapt to changing conditions (Bacciu et al. 2021). Otherwise, the idea of human autonomy is more prevalent in projects that have begun a deeper exploration of the Industry 5.0 concept (BRIDGES 5.0, SME 5.0).

When looking into **Safety and Satisfaction**, the former is seen both in terms of the cybersecurity of the systems developed and implemented within the projects (SME 5.0), and in terms of human safety in relation to the human-machine collaboration (SURE 5.0, PERKS). Safety is considered to be a challenge, both for hardware technology (SME 4.0 with the concept of “safety-aware cyber-physical system”, Ruiz Garcia et al. 2021), especially robotics, and for software (SURE 5.0). Job satisfaction is more related to the flexibility in the workplace (MAIA).

Nevertheless, **the main item that is present in various instances is Collaboration**, which leads into a more creative approach towards the work (see CAPS definition). AI-REDGIO 5.0 aims to create a “collaborative intelligence” platform for Industry 5.0, based on AI analytics, IoT devices “to create a synergistic ecosystem”. The work references several challenges as regards the implementation of the platform in various industries, such as “cost and scalability, training and expertise, workflow integration, and balancing human-AI integration”(AI REDGIO 5.0 2023). Here, the focus is on building **human-machine collaboration**. The majority of the projects tackling such collaboration relate to this type (see also BridgeSMEs and SME4.0). One of the key technologies involved here is AR/VR, which has been integrated in projects with and without human-centric angles. (AGING@WORK, SME 4.0 respectively) In other projects, activities also related to boosting **human to human collaboration** with the help of technologies, but also collaborating with workers to co-create different technologies. AGING@WORK is one such project, where aging workers were involved in designing tools that might improve their well-being at work. Inclusion of their perspectives boosted motivation and willingness to work with the new systems.

The connection between collaboration and creativity is undoubtedly tied to the concept of **co-creation**, as several projects mention it within their activities, from the most ambitious (OPENVERSE) to the most practical applications (in circular manufacturing). DaCAPO project aims to identify new skills for circular manufacturing development and creativity and collaboration are both identified as two of the main skills required (Pinzone and Taisch 2023). ZDMP sees **co-creation and co-design** as core design and development processes for Industry 5.0 applications (Fair, n.d.). Other projects emphasise other requirements for encouraging creativity, namely the **empowerment of workers that can take the form of intrapreneurship opportunities** (BRIDGES 5.0).

3.4 Conclusions

The aim of this chapter was to provide more context into the concept of human-centrism. The methodological approach chosen was an empirical analysis of 21 existing European projects that aimed to tackle research into the adoption of technology that moves away from the Industry 4.0 model.

The diversity of the sample of analysis showcased several perspectives of human-centrism: **technological, business, social alongside human and organisational**. The perspectives were distilled from the qualitative analysis of the project reports and deliverables and confirm the starting point of the SEISMEC project and other projects analysed in this sample, namely that human-centrism lacks a proper definition and requires more conceptual clarity.

Unsurprisingly, building and using technology in accordance with human-centrism was the main dimension that transgressed from the sample of analysis. This can prove to be a rather daunting task since none of the projects analysed provide a definition and/or a clear conceptualisation of the idea of human-centrism. The technology-driven projects present solutions for designing human-centric solutions, such as “human-in-the-loop”, real-time human input that can be fed into the systems, or include specific technologies, especially AR/VR and cobots. This is

also showcased by the overview of the main areas and industries where projects were focused, namely AI and Smart Manufacturing.

The second dimension was more focused on business and economic gains tied to the inclusion of human-centric principles in the organisation and/or business models of the companies/industries that were a part of the research endeavours. Most often, human centrism was translated into introducing “ethical aspects” in the activities of the company. In the majority of the projects analysed, the workers were passive participants in the research and deployment of technology. Adaptation to the new paradigms of technology usage is translated into the need for upskilling and reskilling workers.

The few exceptions that included worker perspectives focused on well-being, flexibility and adaptability to new technologies and their involvement in the co-design of the technology, but still as a support for the company. At a semantic level, privacy, safety, trust, autonomy and human agencies are described as challenges and not as advantages for the company. The business-oriented perspective shapes human-centrism as human acceptance and favours trust-building as a key to more acceptance of technology.

The projects do not pay too much attention to challenges with regards to the organisation of work. The perspective of unions and worker rights is just mentioned in a few instances and highlighted as missing from on-going discussions into the future of work in a human-centric workplace.

The analysis started with a temporary definition of human-centrism, as follows: *an approach to socio-economic activities that is rooted in the needs, experiences, perceptions and values of humans for the design, deployment and evaluation of technology.* The impact of this empirical analysis shows that human-centrism is still tilted towards humans as passive actors. Technology is at the center of research and development in the field. Training, manifested in upskilling, reskilling and overall adaptation to a new type of workplace, are the main measures that target the achievement of human-centrism in the workplace. They are meant to

boost acceptance levels, which is still the main marker of success for human-centrism, instead of building technology with humans from the ground up with co-design, co-creation, and empowerment of workers.

4 Conceptualising CAPS

Empowerment Factors

The modern workplace is undergoing a transformative change, accelerated by digitalisation and the experience of the COVID-19 pandemic. As we navigate into this era, the need for flexibility, support, collaboration and fulfilment in relation to work has increased significantly. This requires a deep understanding of human needs and expectations. In this tension, SEISMEC will demonstrate the SEISMEC shift: industrial practices that combine advances in technology with the empowerment of workers through fair and ethical digital practices. This shift moves from the Industry 4.0 perspective, which puts technology and intensive data analysis at the forefront, to the Industry 5.0 perspective, which focuses on **the relationship between empowering human practices and new technologies**. The aim of SEISMEC is to demonstrate an empowering, human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial technologies. The benefits of human centricity will be measured through four key CAPS empowerment factors:

- Collaboration and Creativity
- Autonomy and Automation
- Productivity and Privacy
- Security and Job Satisfaction

These concepts will ensure human-centred technology applications that can simultaneously empower workers and enhance industrial competitiveness. But what exactly do they mean? Why and how should you apply them in your workplace? We provide a literature review to answer these questions in order to create a SEISMEC framework.

4.1 Collaboration and Creativity

Definitions of Collaboration

The term ‘collaboration’ has a complex and varied history, evolving over time in different disciplines. In a simple definition, collaboration, means interacting with others (Jarvenpaa and Välikangas, 2020, p. 7), but the term has moved from a more traditional, simple notion of ‘working together’ to a multifaceted strategy for creativity, problem-solving, and collective achievement. Collaboration involves mutual goal understanding, pre-emptive task co-management and shared progress tracking (Wang et al., 2020). Industry 5.0 emerges as a way to refocus the emphasis on technology towards one that promotes the interaction and integration of people and technology, demonstrating an interconnection between intelligent digital ecosystems and human practices, with the increasing use of collaborative technologies such as human-human collaboration with the help of advanced technology, human-robot collaboration, and human-AI collaboration (Jafari, Azarian and Yu, 2022; Adel, 2022; Andoni et al., 2019; Aslam et al., 2020; Priadythama, Herdliman and Susmartini, 2020). These types of collaboration are the main focus of our research.

The collaborative interaction between humans and machines will progressively continue to intensify in industrial applications (Adriaensen et al., 2022). For instance, Tóth et al. (2023) recently developed the Industry 5.0 collaboration architecture to frame human-AI collaboration. The goal of this architecture is to investigate and establish a truly integrated human-AI collaboration model, equipped with methods and tools for human-AI driven co-creation.

In the organisational domain, research on human-machine collaboration has emerged and started to exhibit differences in terms of definition, theory, and research contexts (Budhwar et al., 2022; Vrontis et al., 2022; Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003). Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the state of the art of research on human-machine collaboration in organisations and to highlight what types of collaboration exist.

How to achieve greater collaboration?

Importantly, to achieve a greater and an improved level of collaboration, it is all about linear progression. Here, greater collaboration is about a deeper and more integrated partnership aimed at achieving better results. Its presence is critical in all sorts of work environments. As collaboration takes different formats under various circumstances, the question arises what would be necessary steps to achieve greater collaboration. Below, we recommend three steps to achieve this goal:

1. Due to the great benefit of **increased accessibility or availability** of technology-enabled collaboration, organisations could accommodate various new technological solutions for better collaboration (e.g., implementing digital workplace platform, using data sharing platforms, employing virtual reality for team building)
2. Technology-enabled collaboration could provide **improved efficiency** by facilitating decision-making, giving real-time feedback and approvals. Research shows that improved efficiency also potentially increases productivity (Corejova and Chinoracky, 2021; Hopp and Spearman, 2021) (e.g., using a project management tool to map out timelines and delegate tasks, spending more time on brainstorming)
3. Better collaboration could be facilitated by **employee involvement** in developing and implementing advanced technologies (e.g., implementing an employee engagement technology, introducing e-learning for continuous growth)

Human-Human Collaboration with the Help of Technology

Human-human collaboration is complex because it involves “joint intentional action” to bring about a change in the environment (Ludwig, 2020). Bratman's Shared Cooperative Activity framework underlined three core characteristics of human-human collaborations: mutual responsiveness, commitment to joint activity, and commitment to support (Bratman, 1992). To achieve these and have a successful collaboration, the collaborators must have skills such as trust-building, communication, conflict-management, and decision-making skills (Smith, 1996). In addition, it is essential to have effective human-human communication

for fostering a trustworthy social relationship. Effective communication includes active listening, feedback, clarity, and relevance. In doing so, humans can trust and coordinate each other towards the accomplishment of a task together. But what will happen to human-human collaboration when technology is involved?

Today, it is inevitable for humans to involve technology in their daily interactions. Human-human collaboration facilitated by technology involves individuals working together using advanced technologies to achieve their goals efficiently. Technology serves as the primary tool for communication, coordination, and information sharing among team members, enabling rapid progress and goal achievement. A climate should be created in which cross-functional collaboration is supported and visions that can foster innovative work are well communicated (Hadjikosta and Friedrich, 2019; Mumford et al., 2018). Hence, incorporating human interoperability needs could enable the design of systems that promote sharing and collaboration across teams and organisations within technological environments (Handley, 2014). Human interoperability has been defined as ‘the interrelationship between the social system network and the technological system that would provide interoperability across diverse organisational domains to establish sustainable human networks that are reliable, effective, and trust’ (Brown, 2010, p.1). It has been seen as an emerging factor in enhancing information sharing across technology environments (Handley, 2014).

The Human View was used as an additional architectural viewpoint to define and evaluate the human interoperability capabilities. This viewpoint focuses on the human component of a system by capturing data on human roles, tasks, constraints, interactions and metrics. This viewpoint can be used to identify relationships and develop a model of sociotechnical interactions. Based on the Human View, the Human Interoperability model was created. This model provides a better structure to capture interoperability requirements and a mechanism to evaluate the current socio-technical system design. When organisations include human interoperability requirements, the systems can be designed in a way that facilitate sharing and collaboration through technical environments across teams and organisations.

Advances in communication and collaboration technologies have made it possible for groups to collaborate effectively despite the physical dispersion of their members (Cramton, 2001). It is a new era of collaborative activity: using technical solutions for interoperability and alignment (e.g. across time zones) could optimise and standardise operational environments. In addition, it could potentially increase opportunities for both human and collective creativity (Cramton, 2001).

Human-Robot Collaboration

The integration of robots is expected to transform human-robot collaboration in the production context. In recent years, considerable attention has been paid to human-robot collaboration in Industry 5.0 (Xu et al., 2021, Nahavandi, 2019; Gaiardelli et al., 2021). Collaboration between humans and robots in the same workspace provides the opportunity to exchange capabilities, ranging from physical skills to cognitive and social interactions, addressing the increasing demand for adaptability and resilience in modern production systems by defining new roles and skills (Laudante, Formati and Buono, 2022).

It is crucial to determine how humans can effectively and meaningfully collaborate with robots to ensure that work processes and outcomes align with the needs of both individuals and organisations (Kim, 2022). Collaborative robots are being developed to facilitate intuitive interaction with humans (Adel, 2022, Zambon et al., 2019). In this type of interaction, human-centricity is essential, where the relationship between humans and robots is symbiotic and human performance and perception can be enhanced (Asad et al., 2023). Transparency and consistency should be ensured where employees are willing to acknowledge the information provided by the robot (Kim, 2022).

To increase operational flexibility, there is enormous potential in human-robot collaboration, which makes manufacturing versatility more time-efficient (Javaid and Haleem, 2020; Pathak et al., 2019). It is noteworthy that while collaborative robots primarily perform repetitive and hazardous tasks (e.g. heavy lifting),

human collaboration focuses on effective business outcomes, facilitates problem-solving and decision-making, improving the work environment, while enhancing overall intelligence and innovation (Yu, Lou and Gonzalez-Bobes, 2018; Pathak et al., 2019; Gaiardelli et al, 2021). In addition, by relieving humans of repetitive tasks, there is an opportunity to enhance human creativity, flexibility, and judgement in the work process, further motivating individuals to recognise the precision and consistency of robots (Asad et al., 2023) and creatively incorporate several types of robots into the workplace (Nahavandi, 2019).

Human-AI Collaboration

Licklider (1960) introduced the concept of symbiotic computing where the idea of a computer as a partner is an increasingly prevalent metaphor for interaction design. The AI governance literature emphasises the significance of inclusive, cooperative policies to promote ethical, human-centred, and sustainable AI development, and explores innovative collaboration tools to facilitate broad stakeholder discussions (Sigfrids et al, 2023). The goal of human-AI collaboration is to enhance five key aspects of business processes: flexibility, speed, scale, decision-making and personalisation (Wilson and Daugherty, 2018). Organisations need to engage stakeholders in co-creation to envision collaborative opportunities with AI systems for process improvement, supported by new AI and analytics techniques that suggest innovative approaches. However, questions have arisen about how AI collaboration might differ from human-human collaboration, whether AI should have collaboration awareness, ethical considerations for collaborators, etc. Important advantages and disadvantages of human-AI collaboration should be addressed. The potential advantages have a significant impact on productivity, efficiency, and innovation (Tóth et al., 2023).

Advantages (Tóth et al., 2023):

1. The human-centric approach **promotes the cooperation and collaboration** between humans and machines. In this way, it is about fostering a more efficient, resilient, and innovative working environment.

2. In order to **foster an AI-driven creation**, user needs and work culture would be accommodated, leading to more intuitive and easy-to-use tools.
3. **Incorporating human input in real-time, event-driven processes** would lead to more informed decision-making. It might positively impact the overall efficiency and productivity.
4. Human-AI collaboration allows the participation of multiple innovative agents to be **flexible and adapt to different situations and requirements**.

Challenges (Tóth et al., 2023):

1. The existing technological complexity of integration of **innovative agents (AI, IoT, robots) and the challenges** related to interoperability, data privacy and security.
2. Significant **training for workers to adapt** to the new system is important since there might be resistance to change. This leads to the consideration of implementing change management.
3. The implementation and maintenance of such advanced technology can be **costly**. Lastly, there is a risk that several elements of the system may become outdated since technology can change rapidly. So, it is necessary to keep updating and adapting to these rapid changes.

Definitions of Creativity

Creativity is the ability to produce work that is both novel (i.e., original, unexpected) and appropriate (i.e., useful, adaptive to task constraints) (Lubart, 1994; Ochse, 1990; Sternberg, 1988; Sternberg and Lubart, 1991, 1995, 1996; Sternberg and Lubart, 2014). It is seen as a key driver of innovation (Rena, 2023; Dahlbom, 2003; Mbukanma and Goswami, 2023). When combined with resources in the right place by the right people, creativity contributes to innovation in businesses (Shi et al., 2022; Mbukanma and Goswami, 2023). When an innovative approach is taken, change is seen as a creative way of shaping a new context: it increases the focus on opportunities rather than problems (Fitzgerald, Russo and Stolterman, 2002).

To adequately implement human-centric technologies, it is essential these technologies are satisfying, entertaining, helpful, aesthetically pleasing, creative, and emotionally fulfilling for employees (Preece, Rogers and Sharp, 2011). Industry 5.0 is designed to be practical by deliberately emphasising creative research and prioritising knowledge at the forefront of its evolution (Adel, 2022). By combining workflows with intelligent systems, the efficiency of various processes could be enhanced by human creativity. As collaboration becomes the norm in industries, this creates a scenario where human personnel must adapt and find ways to provide new, creative ideas for product development (Adel, 2022). Potential efficiency enhancement necessitates creativity, as innovative solutions can streamline and optimise workflows and processes. In a more collaborative environment, employees aim to adapt because effective teamwork and the integration of different perspectives are essential to generate these innovative solutions and to remain competitive across industries.

Creativity, Artificial Intelligence, and Humans

AI has been described as the replication of human capabilities, including language use and creativity (Stuart Peter, 2020). On the one hand, AI excels at handling repetitive and predictable workflows and is exceptionally good at managing complexity and multi-tasking. On the other hand, humans are more flexible and creative, excelling in knowledge understanding and strategic thinking (Wu et al., 2021). There has been a lot of discussion about the development of AI technologies and challenges such as job replacement. Wu et al. (2021) introduced the new concept of ‘AI creativity’, after discussing and analysing how AI can be used creatively and how AI can enhance human creativity. ‘AI creativity’ refers to the ability of humans and AI to co-live and co-create by playing on each other’s strengths to achieve more (Wu et al., 2021, p. 171). In line with this concept, Wu et al. (2021) created a human-AI co-creation model to explain the creative process in the AI era, with the new possibilities that AI brings. The focus on collaboration not only underscores the importance of teamwork but also advocates for co-creation between humans and AI. The study of Wu et al. (2021) showed that AI creativity has a significant impact in various fields, bringing new possibilities to

human society and individuals, but also new opportunities and challenges in technology, society, and education. The creativity of AI and humans tend to work together to create innovative businesses. Creative minds also often see problems as new opportunities, as there is room for innovation and improvement in every situation.

Advanced technology has created something that has never existed before. AI is designed for interactive use by humans and enhances human creativity (Wu et al., 2021). The proposed human-AI co-creation model is a circular process model with 6 major phases: perceiving, thinking, expressing, collaborating, building, and testing.

Figure 4 - Human-AI co-creation model

In the first phase, AI is used to see where human perception can be enhanced by big data and sensors. Beyond the human senses, AI can transform big data into meaningful information and knowledge, expanding human perspectives both perceptually and intellectually. In the second phase, humans can think deeper and wider with AI, but also efficiently. This can lead to unexpected accomplishments. In the second phase, AI allows humans to think deeper and wider, but also more efficiently. This can lead to unexpected achievements. In the third phase, people can explore more and faster with AI. Humans can have different ideas and optimal ways to present them (e.g. painting, designing, composing, etc.). In the

third phase, humans can explore more and rapidly with AI. Humans can have various ideas and optimal ways to present (e.g., painting, designing, composing etc.). The fourth phase of collaboration is where humans and AI play to each other's strengths. People can always team up with AI, but it is particularly important to understand the limitations and strengths of both human and AI. In the fifth phase and sixth phase is to build and test. Here, production can achieve higher quality and lower cost by simulating and analysing with AI. In the fourth phase of collaboration, humans, and AI play to each other's strengths. Humans can always collaborate with AI, but it is particularly important to understand the limitations and strengths of both humans and AI. The fifth and sixth phases are building and testing. Here production can achieve higher quality and lower costs by simulating and analysing with AI. Thus, the Human-AI Co-Creation Model provides a better understanding of the creative process in the era of AI.

This model explains any 'meaning-making' action to be enhanced by AI and delivered in a more efficient way. Why is this Human-AI Co-creation Model important? AI empowers us throughout the entire creative process, and makes creativity more accessible and inclusive. Furthermore, AI complements human intelligence by consolidating the wisdom from human achievements, making collaboration cross time and space possible. For instance, the sound of mobile phone-recorded coughs can be used to detect asymptomatic COVID-19 infections.

Collaborative Creativity or Creative Collaboration?

Advanced technology is required to enhance collaborative creativity as it increasingly influences the way collaborative creativity develops in organisations (Becker et al., 2015). Collaborative creativity has been interpreted as the ability to contribute and combine ideas in interaction with others (Carlsen, Clegg and Gjersvik, 2012; Harvey, 2014). It has also been defined as reflective reframing, in which individuals respectfully attend to and build on the comments and actions of others (Hargadon and Bechky, 2006, p. 489). However, advanced technology poses challenges: collaborative creativity could be weakened and constrained by

it (Tyre and Orlikowski, 1994; Demetis and Lee, 2018). It can happen by imposing rigid structures, reducing face-to-face interactions, fostering over-reliance on advanced technologies, enforcing algorithmic constraints, diminishing the human element, and causing data overload. These factors collectively limit the spontaneity, flexibility, and diversity of thought that are essential for effective collaborative creativity. One solution may be to foster a culture that values and encourages open communication and interdisciplinary collaboration, where technology is seen as a sociotechnical partner, shaped by societal influences and by the values, needs, and creativity of the people who develop and use it.

4.2 Automation & Autonomy

Definitions of Automation

According to the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), automation refers to a process or system that, under specified conditions, operates without human intervention (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42, 2021). The recent, continuous increase in the deployment of automation technologies is not surprising; automation promises to be cost-effective, efficient and straightforward, making it highly attractive to businesses and organisations (Acemoglu and Johnson, 2023).

For workers, concerns related to increased automation are significant. Countless macro-economic studies have explored these concerns, showing a variety of outcomes on the impact of automation. Frey and Osborne (2017) predict that a large proportion of jobs are at high risk of automation, suggesting significant potential job displacement, while Holm and Lorenz (2022) foresee an extensive disruption in the job market, disproportionately affecting the less skilled workforce. Organisations may overly rely on automation at the cost of creating new job tasks and enhancing worker skills, as they believe it to be a more straightforward, cost-saving alternative to the messier process of workforce management (Acemoglu and Johnson, 2023). In this context, the term *technological unemployment* was coined by John Maynard Keynes (1931) which

highlights the issue of technology eliminating jobs faster than creating new ones. The creation of new tasks or types of employment has begun to stagnate despite the continual development and deployment of new automation technologies (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2019). As a result, automation's economic impacts also unevenly benefit companies and organisations at the expense of workers (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2018). The displacement of workers by automation contributes significantly to these rising inequalities (Acemoglu et al., 2023).

In contrast, it has also been argued that the impact will be less severe due to the variability in job tasks and adaptability of the workforce (Arntz, Gregory and Zierahn, 2017). Brynjolfsson, Mitchell and Rock (2018) highlight the potential for AI to complement human labour, enhancing productivity and creating new job categories. Beyond promising clear benefits to organisations and employers, automation also has the potential of improving work satisfaction in multiple ways. Every industry that achieves rapid increases in productivity does so by relying on diverse types of automation technologies (Gupta and Arora, 2011). Automation brings several benefits: it might reduce production costs, minimise human fatigue, control production process effectively, provide overall better working conditions for the employees, just to name a few (Gupta and Arora, 2011).

One approach through which automation can enhance human efforts is human-machine collaboration. This approach focuses on leveraging technology to integrate advanced technologies into human workflows to augment human capabilities rather than supplant them, thereby maximising efficiency and effectiveness in collaborative tasks (Beer, Fisk and Rogers, 2014). Moreover, automation could benefit workers by reducing the risks associated with working in extreme environments such as deep waters or space. Specifically autonomous observation promises to facilitate looking out for these workers and to record or analyse accidents to prevent them from occurring (Kent and Chernova, 2020, p.1).

Automation has numerous potentials by enhancing human work experiences and by improving product quality and uniformity, decreasing cycle times and effort,

hence reducing labour costs and organising production in a more efficient manner. On the one hand, personalisation and customisation of automation solutions ensure that systems meet individual needs, while on the other hand, effective workload management balances tasks among employees, boosting job satisfaction. Automation could also potentially raise the level of safety for employees and reduce boredom and the possibility of human error (Gupta and Arora, 2011). Health and safety monitoring with advanced technologies could contribute to proactively identifying hazards, safeguarding employee well-being. In addition, lifelong learning and upskilling opportunities provided by automation enable workers to adapt and advance in their careers.

Overall, in order to avoid over-generalisation and to focus on specific impacts and opportunities, a more nuanced understanding emerges when looking at automation through individual technologies, as the impact of advanced technologies varies widely across industries and regions. Given the current trajectory of automation research which often leans towards replacing human roles, there is a pressing need for greater investment, policy interventions in technologies that complement human abilities. Such an initiative could dramatically reshape the impact of automation, promoting more equitable technological progress (Acemoglu et al., 2023).

A Taxonomy of Automation Types

A taxonomy of automation types allows for the navigation around the complexities inherent in the development of automated technologies. Using vehicles as an example, Seppelt et al. (2018) propose a binary human-centric taxonomy of vehicle automation in which the only distinction is made between if the consumer must “drive” the technology or if they are the ones being “riding” it. Automated technologies in which the user is the driver include safety assistance, driver assistance and supervised driving. On the other end of the spectrum, the user is riding the technology when the technology intermittently self-drives or is entirely self-driving (p. 18). In a larger context, we may refer to this binary taxonomy in order to distinguish between all types of automation. What seems

to be the most important distinction from a user perspective is to understand when they are responsible for taking the wheel or when the technology fully takes over their task (Seppelt et al., 2018, p. 18).

The differentiation between consumer-driven and technology-driven roles in automated technologies ultimately leads to an automated versus autonomous dichotomy. When roles in automated technologies are primarily influenced by consumer demands, they tend to focus more on fulfilling specific needs. On the other hand, technology-driven roles prioritise the development and advancement of the technology itself, aiming for greater autonomy and independence from direct human input. Hence, differentiation happens by highlighting to what degree human intervention or control is involved and relied on. In consumer-driver scenarios, individuals have the responsibility for executing tasks, technology has a supportive, assisting role in completing tasks, meaning that automation mostly serves to augment human capabilities. In this scenario, human control remains crucial and central. However, in technology-driven scenarios, where technology self-drives or is entirely self-driving, systems are primarily responsible for task execution where minimal or no human intervention is required. In this scenario, autonomy becomes a defining feature. Overall, this clear distinction highlights the disparity between automated systems, where automation is either human-directed or where technology operates independently.

Automation and AI

Automation through AI technology poses similar concerns as traditional forms of automation, such as the displacement of workers and dimming of worker voice as a result of increased monitoring and surveillance, it also opens the possibility for new ways of improving work conditions (Acemoglu et al., 2023). For example, automation through AI has the potential to decrease inequality by enabling workers in lower-tier positions to undertake higher valued tasks (Acemoglu et al., 2023). Simultaneously, it can enhance work performance, but this may come at the cost of unsustainability accelerating the pace of work and diminishing employee autonomy (Holm and Lorenz, 2022).

AI systems can be evaluated by comparing their degree of automation and the extent to which they are under external control. When classifying a system on this spectrum, some key factors need to be considered such as:

- determining whether there is external supervision,
- system's ability to understand and confidently act in all states,
- the systems reactivity,
- consider if the system continues functioning up,
- the degree of adaptability of the system,
- system's capacity to assess its own performance,
- the ability of the system to make proactive decisions and plans (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42, 2021).

Considering human-centric innovations, these evaluation steps highlight the importance of understanding the continuity of automation or the absence of it. On one end of the spectrum lies a complete lack of automation, where the operator fully controls the system. At the other end, the system is fully autonomous. Here, an autonomous system is characterised by its ability to perform tasks with a high degree of autonomy (HLEG AI, 2020). Practically, it describes a system capable of altering its operating domain or objectives independently, without the need for external intervention, control, or oversight (ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42, 2021).

Definitions of Autonomy

In everyday language, autonomy generally refers to the capacity of an individual, agent, or system to make decisions and govern themselves independently with minimal or no external assistance (Estevez Almenzar et al., 2022). However, autonomy can be placed in different contexts such as in organisational sciences, and technology.

Autonomy in Organisational Sciences

In the workplace, autonomy manifests in two forms. The first type relates to the work itself, encompassing decision-making over work processes, the opportunity

to choose the timing of work tasks, and the ability to choose one's work methods. The second, often called boundary control, pertains to influence over when and where one works (Parker and Grote, 2020). Both these forms of professional autonomy are essential for achieving successful outcomes in both business performance and employee satisfaction (Holm and Lorenz, 2022).

Autonomy in the workplace is highly beneficial for several reasons. Firstly, autonomy allows individuals to actively manage stress resulting from demands in their environment (Karasek, 1979). Secondly, according to Hackman and Oldham's job characteristics model (1976), job autonomy not only boosts meaning, motivation, job performance, creativity, and proactivity, but also decreases employee turnover. Thirdly, high autonomy in work settings facilitates efficient decision-making, allowing for local management of disturbances in work processes without the need for hierarchical escalation (Wall et al., 2002).

Autonomy in Technology

Machines are considered to have autonomy when they rely on programmed algorithms, AI and machine learning to interpret information and make action-related decisions. Interestingly, AI researchers use the term “autonomy” as a metaphor to refer to a diverse set of different types of computational behaviour (Johnson and Verdicchio, 2017). However, non-experts have a different interpretation of autonomy as it is often linked to machines possessing similar autonomy as humans have (i.e. freedom to choose certain behaviours). This diversity of meanings of the concept often lead to miscommunication as in the eyes of the public, autonomy could appear as something with free will and own interests, entirely out of human control which creates a matter of concern and fear (Johnson and Verdicchio, 2017). Mellamphy (2021) outlines three different scenarios in which humans are 1. entirely at the centre of control and command; 2. humans and technologies share control; 3. humans' oversight is completely removed. She suggests focusing more on critical ways of revising these interactions.

In the field of computational sciences, Jennings (2000) defines autonomous agents as entities that maintain control over both their internal states and their behaviours. Autonomy in this context means that these agents operate independently, actively determining their actions on their own (Jennings, 2000, pp. 280-283). However, within this general concept, different types of autonomy (e.g., social autonomy, norm-autonomy, environmental autonomy, agent-autonomy) are defined according to the environment or the agents involved in the execution of decisions and tasks (Carabelea, Boissier and Florea, 2004).

Definitions of autonomy in the field of engineering add into account a strong awareness of the question of responsibility. The actions of an agent with autonomy originate from its own objectives and are executed on its own accord, therefore it alone bears all responsibility for its decisions and actions. In other words, when an agent operates autonomously, no one else can be held accountable for its actions (Sparrow, 2007, p. 63).

Accountability

Automated systems can operate independently from human control, formulating their own rules and actions, which can lead to unpredictable and potentially harmful outcomes. Automated systems' ability to act without oversight leaves little space for the incorporation of human intuition and judgement, which are critical in considering the consequences of actions (Ulgen, 2021, p. 1). This challenges traditional concepts of legal liability and responsibility as the absence of human interference in the decision-making process complicates the determination of who is accountable when things go wrong (Ulgen, 2021, p. 4).

Defining a singularly responsible actor is always difficult, given the multiple actors and parties involved in the creation and deployment of an automated (AI) system. Besides the potential negative consequence of watering down a sense of responsibility in each of these actors, the involvement of such a vast spectrum of agents also ensures that responsibility is expected at every level of the system's development and deployment (Ulgen, 2021, p. 6).

In specific cases of AI use, even the most careful planning and design cannot make up for the unpredictability and chaos of real-world environments. Therefore, developers must integrate non-deterministic factors (like contextual factors or probabilistic models) into AI systems or rely on human judgement and feedback when needed (Ulgen, 2021, p. 13). Integrating human oversight is one solution to this problem (Ulgen, 2021, p. 13). Therefore, human-centric automation approaches aim to ensure that systems remain transparent and reliable by facilitating sufficient user influence over technical processes. However, as automation increases and the systems become more complex, maintaining human control proves to be challenging (Parker and Grote, 2020).

Meaningful Human Control (MHC)

One approach to integrating human judgement in the operational process of systems is Meaningful Human Control (MHC). According to this approach, humans should ultimately remain in control of technology by taking an active role in operational decisions (Calvert et al., 2020, p. 479). It emphasises that mere human involvement is insufficient; control in this context refers to the controlling agent's ability to direct or influence events according to their preferences (Calvert et al., 2020, p. 493). As illustrated above, this type of control is particularly important when autonomous systems are deployed in complex, dynamic and unpredictable environments, necessitating more than just human presence to prevent mistakes and ensure accountability (Calvert et al., 2020, p. 490).

The role of a human in the decision-making process needs to be substantial. However, this does not require that a human operator continuously manages every aspect of the operation. On the contrary, it argues for a design where autonomous systems and human operations coexist. It proposes that both the system's design and operation should be optimised to align with the intentions of the human operator. This design should foster behaviours that reflect human intentions, thereby maintaining human-centric operational control even as the system executes functions independently (Calvert et al., 2020, p. 490).

As a result, automation that follows MHC principles does not diminish autonomy but reshapes it. Although integrating this type of control may make the design of these technologies more challenging, it also facilitates a balance where increased system autonomy does not detract from but rather enhances human control (Calvert et al., 2020, p. 491). The MHC approach ensures that as technological systems become more autonomous, they do not reduce human autonomy. Instead, they evolve in ways that enhance their reliability while firmly embedding human values and control at their core.

Human Autonomy Meets Automation: Shaping Tomorrow’s Innovations

Autonomy and automation pose complexities within a human-centric framework and existing literature on the two terms has shown that they are not mutually exclusive but rather highly intertwined. Processes of automation may create the potential to infringe on others’ autonomy. The introduction of new technologies and the work practices associated with them can disrupt human autonomy, especially in high-skill roles (Parker and Grote, 2020; Holm and Lorenz, 2022). At present, inappropriate deployment might lead to disadvantageous outcomes such as unemployment, economic inequalities, and decreased job satisfaction.

SEISMEC’s focus is on the enhancement of autonomy through automation and vice versa, while empowering employees by streamlining menial, dangerous and ineffective tasks. However, translating this into practice presents numerous challenges as definitions of the lines between autonomy and automation are blurred, the two concepts have some overlapping features from certain perspectives.

Evaluating both the autonomy of advanced technological tools and the external control becomes crucial, which also increases the need for considerations of accountability and responsibility in decision-making processes. The dichotomy between technology-driven and human-driven systems highlights the need for a greater understanding of their implications as this differentiation makes provisions for exploring taxonomies of automation types.

To conclude, the goal of achieving human-centric innovations demands a balancing act between automation and autonomy where technology serves to augment human abilities rather than weaken them. By embracing principles of meaningful human control and prioritising the greater level of autonomy, organisations can effectively address the complexities of automation to empower individuals, create human-centric work environments, foster creativity and uphold human dignity in the light of technological advancements.

4.3 Privacy and Productivity

Definitions of Privacy

While defining privacy is difficult, privacy can be understood as sharing information outside socially agreed contextual boundaries (Finn, Wright and Friedewald, 2013). The concept ‘privacy’ includes multiple dimensions (e.g., legal, social-psychological, economic, political), and some privacy theorists have attempted to create taxonomies or categories of privacy. Roger Clarke (1997) defined four categories of privacy (privacy of person, privacy of personal behaviour, privacy of personal communication, and privacy of personal data). Based on Roger Clarke’s (1997) four categories of privacy, Finn, Wright and Friedewald (2013) expanded and included the four categories to seven types of privacy:

- privacy of person
- **privacy of behaviour and action**
- **privacy of communication**
- **privacy of data**
- **privacy of thoughts and feelings**
- **privacy of location and space**
- privacy of association

All types of privacy should be protected in legislation, however, not all types of privacy will be described in the current research. For this research, we will only address the types of privacy in **bold**.

Impact of Advanced Technologies on Privacy

Human-centricity is about putting the human's well-being, preferences and needs in the centre of industries where we capture the value of advanced technologies (Ivanov, 2023). However, it is not always easy to guarantee the protection of an individual's privacy in our high-tech surveillance society. Some researchers have focused on the impact of advanced technology on several types of privacy. For instance, surveillance practices are related to the privacy of behaviour and action and the privacy of location and space. Surveillance and privacy are two interlinked yet often opposing concepts in the digital era. The relationship between surveillance and privacy is fundamentally about finding a good balance between the need for security and the protection of individuals' freedoms. Surveillance involves watching and monitoring employee's actions during working hours using employer equipment or property in order to uncover specific wrongdoing (Sarpong and Rees, 2014).

Here, we can take the privacy of behaviour and action and the privacy of location and space into account. Some reasons for surveillance practices are for performance reviews, business information, security and safety. It can lead to an increase in productivity, reduce absenteeism and ensure the security, health and safety of employees. However, according to the British trade union Amicus, monitoring and surveillance can undermine individual's privacy, they can also create high levels of stress and anxiety (Amicus Guide, 2005; Sarpong and Rees, 2014). A study of Sarpong and Rees (2014) showed that monitoring technology in the workplace lets employees feel watched when they are making their own tea or going to the toilet. Importantly, it's essential to ensure that employees are informed in advance about any surveillance or monitoring protocols implemented in the workplace, such as signing an informed consent. This leads to a second privacy issue on digital consenting, which is the privacy on behaviour and action and the privacy of data and image.

Digital consenting is about giving or withdrawing consent in the digital space (Human and Cech, 2021). Giving the end-user consent is important in digital regulations such as the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), which considers the protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of

personal data as a fundamental right. Previous research showed that a lot of people do not seem to be empowered to practise their digital right to privacy and lawful consenting (due to not having the necessary and relevant information). To tackle this, Human and Cech (2021) proposed a human-centric framework to empower individual's right to consent by interdisciplinary and multidimensional. In this framework, consenting is a socio-cognitive action which includes cognitive, collective, and contextual dimensions. They applied this framework to evaluate practices of tech companies such as Google, Amazon, Facebook, Apple and Microsoft. They have concluded that these companies do not follow a human-centric approach towards obtaining individuals' consents. This is affecting the privacy of behaviour and action, and the privacy of data and image. Previous researchers showed that people are not always aware of giving their personal data away when participating in online activities, which can raise issues.

Another privacy issue is on the privacy of personal data. As mentioned before, the privacy of thoughts and feelings has been influenced by advanced technologies. Hallinan et al. (2014) addressed neuro data (the description of data directly representing the function of the human brain) (Hallinan et al., 2014, p. 55) issues arising from two levels: legal technical level and fundamental level. The issue on the legal technical level is regarding the formal applicability of the definitions and systems of the data protection framework. The issue on the fundamental level is regarding the interests in neuro data, specifically related to the protection of the mind. The mind represents a uniquely sensitive and intimate space in the individual's private sphere. Neuro data is personal data which is relevant to data protection.

Previous studies showed that advanced technologies have impacted an individual's privacy. This allows us to provide companies guidance on human-centric approaches to foster a workplace where employees experience guarantees of privacy.

Definitions of Productivity

The term of productivity has a dynamic nature. It is not a uniform, universal concept. It is often vaguely conceptualised, and poorly understood even though it has been a widely discussed topic of a variety of disciplines across academic and commercial circles. The existence of different definitions under various conditions lead to confusion when productivity is applied as a practical tool or measurement (Björkman, 1992).

At a basic level, it is generally defined as the relation of output (i.e. produced goods) to input (i.e. consumed resources) for a specific production situation (e.g. manufacturing transformation process) and is one of the most important basic variables that govern economic production activities (Tangen, 2002a; Singh, Motwani and Kumar, 2000; Rogers, 1998; Sumanth, 1994). Bernolak (1997) explained what productivity entails in terms of manufacturing: it refers to the efficiency and effectiveness of utilising resources to produce goods or provide services. In this interpretation, resources encompass all human and physical factors, including both individuals involved in production and the assets, and the assets utilised (e.g. machinery, tools, raw materials).

There exists a widespread awareness of the significance of achieving high productivity levels (Björkman, 1992). High productivity results from the synergy between high levels of efficiency and effectiveness within the transformation process (Tangen, 2005). However, it is important to note that producing goods for which there is no demand is not productive, regardless of the rationality and efficiency of the production system (Björkman, 1992).

It has been concluded that it would be important to establish a clear productivity definition in a company setting and, in the industry, more generally which could be beneficial to a company's overall improvement work (Tangen, 2002a). As it is a relative term, it cannot be deemed to increase or decrease without comparison, either of changes over time or of variations from a benchmark at a specific moment in time (e.g. a competitor or another department) (Tangen, 2005).

Modern productivity paradox

Advancements in productivity typically stem from technological innovations and their wider impacts (Lee, 2020). Generally, productivity improvements are driven by advanced technologies or new ways of organising production processes (Acemoglu, Aghion and Zilibotti, 2006; Griffith, Redding and Van Reenen, 2004). However, given the remarkable advances in technology, such as AI, machine learning, robotics, cloud computing and advanced software solutions, the question arises why productivity growth hasn't accelerated. This question has been raised by Parteka and Kordalska (2023), who reflect on the slowdown in productivity growth despite tremendous technological advances. This phenomenon is known as the 'modern productivity paradox' (Brynjolfsson, 1993).

An explanation is needed as to why technological advances do not have a positive and direct impact on productivity records. As for now, research focusing on the relationship between advanced technology implementation and productivity is still limited, primarily due to conceptual and methodological challenges. Nonetheless, the rapid advancement and extensive application of AI technology have the potential to significantly alter organisations' methods of production, thus impacting their productivity (Parteka and Kordalska, 2023).

Human-Centricity, Advanced Technologies, and Productivity

Unlike research on the modern productivity paradox, results of recent empirical studies, both at the industry and organisational levels, suggest a positive and significant relationship between the adoption of digital technologies and productivity across all sectors within an industry (Bloom et al., 2007; Nahavandi, 2019; Draca, Sadun and Van Reenen, 2006; Syverson, 2011). In addition, organisations that combine advanced technologies with workforce skill development are more likely to be more productive than those that do not have such practices (Brynjolfsson and McAfee, 2014). For instance, integrating AI and machine learning with continuous employee training could help organisations facilitate informed decision-making and strategic planning processes.

The benefits of digital technologies within a sector are generally linked to firm-level productivity gains (Gal et al., 2019). Productivity gains are greater for digital adopters, and even more for companies investing in at least one AI-related technology (Nucci, Puccioni and Ricchi, 2023). By focusing on quality control, predictive maintenance, and process optimisation, advanced technologies will help increase overall productivity and efficiency (Rao et al, 2024).

Productivity is often associated with enabling employees by creating an environment where employees are empowered to excel, rather than merely increasing pressure to perform. (Boxall et al., 2019; Boxall & Winterton, 2018). According to Boxall et al. (2019), productivity improvements are achieved when employees are provided with the necessary skills, resources, and autonomy to perform their tasks effectively. Similarly, Boxall & Winterton (2018) emphasise that enabling employees through supportive management practices, continuous learning opportunities, and participative decision-making processes contributes to a more productive workforce.

Enhancing job quality and employee well-being is increasingly recognised as crucial for improving productivity and fostering shared prosperity (Guest, Knox and Warhurst, 2022). Investing in human workers' skills and well-being is essential for driving productivity growth (Adel, 2022). Remarkably, the OECD also promotes job quality as a means to enhance employee well-being and productivity, asserting that it aligns with the interests of both management and stakeholders (Freeman, Wicks and Parmar, 2004). From a human centric perspective, a production system that prioritises human needs should enhance the productivity of employees and the operational efficiency of organisations among others (Graessler and Poehler, 2019). Technological innovations and human workforce are essential for maximising the benefits of advanced technologies, increasing productivity, and achieving quality objectives in manufacturing (Mital and Pennathur, 2004).

Human-complementary AI and productivity

AI technology has been positively associated with productivity and employment (Yang, 2022). The move towards "human-complementary AI" holds promise for driving greater productivity gains and potentially mitigating economic inequality (Acemoglu, Autor and Johnson, 2023). Empirical studies validate the transformative impact of human-centric AI on worker productivity, with significant increases observed following implementation (Shchepkina et al., 2024).

The integration of AI technology in industrial sectors is set to revolutionise productivity by upgrading tasks of human employees, automating repetitive operations, providing data-driven insights and extending employees' flexibility and decision-making capabilities (Block, Fisch and van Praag, 2016). However, understanding the nuanced effects of AI deployment on worker productivity requires systematic empirical investigation. Worker productivity may be substantially impacted by a well-planned integration of AI in the workplace (Nucci, Puccioini and Ricchi, 2023, Parteka and Kordalska, 2023; Chowdhury et al., 2022; Yang 2022). As AI technologies are increasingly integrated into various industries, empirical studies of how human-centred AI affects worker productivity will be possible.

Initiatives that support employee training and skill development play an important role in facilitating efficient collaboration with AI systems and maximising employee productivity (Nahavandi, 2019; Shchepkina et al., 2024). Collaborative problem solving becomes an integral part of improving productivity (Mishra and Mishra, 2009). Improved skills contribute to organisational efficiency, help motivate individuals, and deliver tangible results (Adel, 2022). Human-centric AI prioritises individuals and communities while improving efficiency, productivity, safety, accuracy, and real-time data analytics in work environments (Adel, 2022; Wan and Leirimo, 2023).

Monitoring Dilemma: Productivity Gains vs. Privacy Concerns

Privacy and productivity are significant problems since the boundaries between formal and informal places of work are blurred (Evans, 2007). For instance, employers can forbid employees to take their laptop computers outside the formal workplace because employees should be responding very quickly to customer needs. However, in the modern workplace, electronic monitoring of employees' activities to measure work performance has become commonplace, it has become the 'community norm' (Eivazi, 2011). The implications of monitoring for privacy and its effects on productivity are greatly debated. While such monitoring has long been justified as a means of improving work performance, the conflict between employees' interests and employers' interests in the workplace has become controversial (Lee and Kleiner, 2003). It is well reflected in Bino Idonije's work (2022; Nwosu, 2022, p. 4), the linkage between privacy and productivity is addressed clearly:

'There is going to be, in fact there already is, a blurring of the lines between workplace and personal space, and employees will need to manage their expectations of privacy from the employer. Employers have a vested interest in monitoring productivity especially in cases where the compensation model is tied to the number of hours invested in the work. However, employer's must be upfront about the monitoring systems implemented and it goes without saying, that they must be within legal boundaries.'

Performance monitoring is considered a managerial right of employers which is also related to their business productivity (Eivazi, 2011). It refers to the act of employers monitoring employees during work hours (e.g., tracking computer activities, email and network usage, time spent on tasks etc.). One of the most frequent reasons given by employers for their use of technological surveillance at work is productivity loss (Eivazi, 2011). Low productivity can have a negative impact on business outcomes which is fatal for an organisation. Employers are concerned about their employees engaging in personal activities such as browsing the internet or sending personal emails during work hours which has proven to be distracting, thereby reducing productivity, and potentially leading to

financial losses for businesses (Eivazi, 2011; Kierkegaard, 2005). Therefore, it is often argued that monitoring employees is essential for an organisation to measure efficiency and obtain productivity.

As stated, employers are justified in obtaining employee information relevant to job performance. However, the question arises: what the best approach could be to solve the conflict between the interests of the employer and the rights of the employee at the workplace? On the one hand, proponents of electronic monitoring argue that it can help reduce employee misconduct, increase productivity, prevent the unauthorised disclosure of confidential information, prevent corporate liability, and minimise the risk of legal liability. It can help motivate employees to feel committed and work hard as monitoring provides employers a picture of how productive employees are (Lee and Kleiner, 2003).

On the other hand, the intensification of control issues and of information security has put employees under stress. According to Lee, Lee and Kim (2016), two major stress factors are work overload and the invasion of privacy. Lee, Lee and Kim (2016) showed that negative effects of stress lead to reduced employee productivity. Excessive monitoring can be counterproductive, as it may create a sense of violation of privacy among employees. Especially in environments where employees feel their privacy is compromised, this can lead to increased stress levels, anger, anxiety, depression, fatigue, and decreased productivity (Flanagan, 1993).

Overall, the relationship between monitoring, privacy, information security and productivity is complex and multifaceted. Both productivity and quality control are critical factors in the operation of a business (Lee and Kleiner 2003). Although the practice of monitoring has benefits for productivity and quality control, there are potential negative effects on employee morale and well-being. A productive and healthy work environment should strike a balance between the necessary level of monitoring and maintaining employee privacy.

4.4 Safety and (job) Satisfaction

Definitions of Safety

Safety is a fundamental part of the occupational health and safety discipline. Its main objective is to promote and maintain “the highest degree of physical, mental and social well-being of workers that is the ‘whole person’ in all occupations; prevention among workers of adverse effects on health caused by their working conditions; the protection of workers in their employment from risks resulting from factors adverse to health; the placing and maintenance of workers in an occupational environment adapted to physical and mental needs; the adaptation of work to humans” (Ratna and Kaur, 2016, p. 1). In general, safety has been defined as “a state in which hazards and conditions leading to physical, psychological or material harm are controlled in order to preserve the health and well-being of individuals and the community” (Maurice et al., 2001, p. 237). Management systems aim to promote safety excellence as it is their legal obligation to ensure the safety and health of workers in all aspects related to work and protect them from occupational health and safety risks (European Commission, 2016).

Organisational responsibility for safety has been emphasised in the literature (Perrow, 1999; Williamson et al., 1997). The main objective of industrial safety is to protect workers from illness, harm and injury (Ebert et al., 2023). Management strategies begin with creating a safety culture, including leadership for safety, open error reporting, internal oversight, better hiring practices, alignment with industry standards, and safety-focused training (Berry et al., 2016; Guldenmund, 2000; Shneiderman, 2020a).

The sociotechnical systems approach enhances workplace safety by considering multiple system factors (Carayon et al., 2015). This approach views safety as an emergent property of system interactions. The innermost layer represents the work system, viewed from a human-centric perspective, showing the role of humans in relation to tools and technologies. These factors interact,

addressing human-related concerns within each system element. The socio-organisational context (second layer) concerns the social and organisational culture within the company, influencing the effectiveness of work system design. The third layer refers to the social, economic, legal, and political environment, or the external environment. Firm-specific cultures and system interfaces are influenced by the larger work and occupational context. Workers play a significant role in “producing” emergent workplace safety (Carayon et al., 2015).

Figure 5 - The model of sociotechnical system for workplace safety (Carayon et al. 2015).

Safety participation consists of voluntary behaviours that affect workplace safety indirectly (e.g., attending safety meetings, helping co-workers), while safety compliance consists of performing required safety activities (e.g., wearing protective equipment, following procedures) (Beus, McCord and Zohar, 2016).

Remarkable advancements in safety could be made by:

1. broadening the unit of analysis to the sociotechnical systems level (including human interdependencies) & developing a unified sociotechnical systems approach to workplace safety (Carayon et al., 2015);
2. Assessing dimensions such as resilience and the adaptive role of workers in creating and improving safety (Carayon et al., 2015);
3. addressing the fundamental challenges associated with advanced technologies, emerging industries, and ever-changing workforce (Holden et al., 2013; Carayon et al., 2014);

4. creating safe, reliable, and trustworthy systems through solid technical practices, open management strategies and well-designed independent oversight structures Shneiderman, 2020b).

The impact of advanced technologies on safety: a human-centric approach

The integration of human-centric approaches across industries has gained significant attention for its benefits, such as accident prevention and energy saving (Guo et al., 2023). Human safety is fundamental; thus, human-centric systems place human operators, their knowledge, and skills in key positions (Yi et al., 2024). By incorporating human-centred design principles, organisations can align technology with workers' needs and behaviours, improving safety and usability (Wong et al., 2023). However, few studies have examined safety issues with human-centric systems.

Safety management is vital for ensuring human-centred manufacturing and reducing human-related risks. Industry 5.0 manufacturing requires integrating knowledge-driven, human-machine-environmental safety, posing three main challenges for the future (Wang et al., 2023):

1. insight challenge: the complex nature of interactions created by complex environments, high-risk processes, and multiple workstations,
2. machine comprehensibility challenge: the difficulty machines have in predicting potential real-time safety incidents,
3. adaptability challenge: developing safety management methods adaptable to different manufacturing environments.

Existing research shows that narrowly identifying injury events as local failures or focusing solely on workers' exposure to workplace hazards can cause additional problems (Carayon et al., 2015). Other challenges include data privacy and cybersecurity issues, lack of technological readiness, and insufficient consideration of health, safety, and environmental risks in human-machine collaboration (Wanasinghe et al., 2021). Leveson's (2016) systems-theoretic accident model and processes (STAMP) framework emphasises that safety should be viewed as a control problem rather than just a failure issue. By incorporating system-theoretic process analysis (STPA) and safety-guided

design principles, organisations can better identify and mitigate risks throughout the entire system lifecycle. This holistic approach ensures that safety measures are integrated from the outset, addressing potential hazards before they appear as failures, thereby creating more resilient and safer work environments.

Effective implementation of new technologies to improve workplace safety involves several steps:

1. Safe, digitally enabled environment (deploying advanced technologies like wearables, AI, machine learning algorithms, cloud computing etc.) (Wanasinghe et al., 2021);
2. Personalised human training (understanding safety management adaptability and causality of unsafe conditions) (Tsiakas et al., 2017; Guo et al., 2023);
3. Safety-aware control schemes: (continuous improvement of management strategies, training programs, operational practices, and root-failure analysis) (Shneiderman, 2020b);
4. Collaborative systems' design (establishing complete knowledge about production scenarios to adapt collaborative plans and create safe control paradigms) (Umbrico et al., 2022). The human component's role is significant for efficient collaboration (Tsiakas et al., 2017);
5. Intelligent manufacturing systems (reflecting human behaviour, machine states, environmental influence, and their interactions) (Wang et al., 2023). Multimodal human behaviour monitoring and assessment can reinforce safety and training in collaborative tasks, providing a better understanding of human behaviour and effective collaboration conditions (Tsiakas et al., 2017).

Overall, technology applied for safety ensures the protection of workers' physical and mental integrity. A human-centric approach to implementing advanced technologies contributes to resilience, sustainability, and effectiveness (Gamberini and Pluchino, 2024).

Surveillance practices for a safer environment

Safety monitoring, used as a form of surveillance, is imperative in risk-filled work environments. Employers engage in workplace surveillance to improve safety, which includes safety observations, worker feedback, incident reports, and skill assessment. Advanced technologies can evaluate performance, provide feedback on decision-making, danger recognition, and emergency response capabilities, reinforcing safety skills.

However, the implementation of technology for safety management involves collecting personal data, raising ethical and legal issues regarding tracking and monitoring employees (Oesterreich and Teuteberg, 2016). Excessive monitoring without clear reasons can lead to reduced job satisfaction and confidence in the organisation (Ball, 2021). Proper communication of the motives behind monitoring and transparency can improve employee performance and safety acceptance (Ravid et al., 2020; Jacobs et al., 2019).

AI Safety

AI's transformative role in workplace safety can be beneficial for many organisations (Bullock et al., 2024). AI systems play a growing role in management, process, and product development (Cebulla, Szpak and Knight, 2023). However, AI's contribution to addressing occupational safety and health concerns is not fully understood (Pishgar et al., 2021). For instance, various questions arise (also closely related to automation): how easily organisations overlook what is happening in the 'background' of automated processes, and how systemic problems can arise there with very little chance of detection.

Worker safety in AI contexts refers to protecting privacy from AI intrusion and preventing associated harm (Cebulla, Szpak and Knight, 2023). AI safety focuses on designing systems that allow employees to control AI safely (Srivastava, 2021). AI safety also involves mitigating accident risks from machine learning systems, where unintended harmful behaviours may emerge (Amodei et al., 2016), such as biases present in the training data, errors in applications, incorrect predictions or classifications, data privacy violations and model exploitation. AI-driven safety tools identify and prevent potential hazards by processing vast amounts of

information quickly, providing real-time monitoring and alerts, and enhancing workplace safety (Shah et al., 2022). AI can reduce workplace accidents, improve work quality, and increase efficiency (Krainiuk, Buts and Barbashyn, 2023).

However, AI integration also poses risks such as privacy, security, fairness, and economic impacts (Amodei et al., 2016). Increased monitoring and tracking can lead to worker stress and anxiety (Moore, 2019). Addressing workers' concerns and prioritising a 'human-in-command' approach can mitigate these risks (De Stefano, 2020). Understanding AI techniques and their impact on worker health and safety is critical as AI applications grow (Pishgar et al., 2021).

Ethical guidelines for AI in the workplace should address how AI reshapes workplace relationships and impacts health and safety (Cebulla, Szpak and Knight, 2023). Developing robust, beneficial AI that prioritises safety and controllability ensures safe human-AI interactions (Srivastava, 2021; Russell, Dewey and Tegmark, 2015).

In conclusion, while AI and advanced technologies offer benefits in efficiency and productivity, organisations must consider workplace safety implications. By understanding potential risks, implementing ethical guidelines, and prioritising safety, workplaces can realise these technologies' full potential while ensuring employee well-being. AI system development and use should adhere to ethical guidelines to uphold human autonomy, dignity, and privacy, aligning with EU and state laws (Heilala and Parchegani, 2023). Reframing ethics as occupational health and safety can reduce organisational resistance to new AI safety processes (Cebulla, Szpak and Knight, 2023).

Definitions of Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is one of the most critical aspects in employee well-being and organisational success. Locke (1976) defined job satisfaction as “...a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences” (p. 1300). In this definition of Locke, job satisfaction is conceptualised as an affective reflection to work (Zhu, 2013). But throughout the

years, other definitions were given from another perspective with the conclusion that job satisfaction is a multifaceted concept that also includes cognitive and behavioural components.

Job satisfaction is more the extent to which employees are satisfied or dissatisfied with their job (Ali et al., 2014). It can act as both an independent and dependent variable, meaning that job satisfaction can be the cause of organisational success but also the effect of an organisational outcome. On the one hand, job satisfaction directly and negatively relates to employees' turnover intentions (intentions to quit their job), which leads to actual turnover. Chen et al. (2011) examined how job satisfaction (independent variable) systematically improves or declines for change in employees' turnover intentions. On the other hand, the study of Ali et al. (2014) examined the relationship between five job characteristics (autonomy, skill variety, task significance, task identity, and feedback) and job satisfaction (dependent variable) among managers in fast food outlets. They have found that the relationship between the job characteristics and job satisfaction is positive.

Theories of Job Satisfaction

Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow's hierarchy of needs was a helpful starting point to examine important factors for job satisfaction.

Figure 6 - Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1970)

Maslow (1970) stated that individuals will satisfy basic-level needs before climbing further in the pyramid to satisfy higher-level needs. Individuals seek to satisfy physiological needs first because these are the basic needs required to sustain life (e.g. food, water, sleep). Once physiological needs are satisfied, safety and security are next. They represent the need to be free of fear of physical danger, the need to be free of deprivation of physiological needs. Next, the need of love and belonging refers to belonging to and being accepted by different groups. After, the need for personal recognition and esteem or recognition from others should be satisfied. When the need of self-esteem is satisfied, individuals seek to satisfy the need to maximise one's potential and want to become what one can become. An important note for this theory is that individuals cannot pursue the next higher need in the hierarchy until her or his currently recognised need is completely satisfied. In the context of work, these needs can be used to explain job satisfaction (Hassard and Cox, 2014). The need for safety and security for employees can be satisfied through the feeling of being physically safe in their work environment, but also having job security. If these needs are satisfied, the need of belonging to the workplace should be satisfied. This can manifest through positive relationships with colleagues and supervisors, but also having the feeling that an employee is part of their team or organisation or not. Then, the employee

will seek to feel if they are valued and appreciated by their colleagues, supervisor, or organisation. Lastly, an employee will seek to self-actualise.

Motivator-Hygiene Theory

The motivator-hygiene theory identifies two major aspects in a work situation: motivator factors and hygiene factors (Herzberg, 1966). Motivators (e.g., benefits, recognition) lead to job satisfaction and superior performance (Whitsett and Winslow, 1967). Hygiene factors (e.g., working conditions, job security) prevent dissatisfaction but do not contribute to satisfaction or lasting motivation. Satisfaction and dissatisfaction are not opposites. Hygiene factors address the need to avoid pain, comparable to Maslow's deficiency motives (Maslow, 1970). These needs reduce pain but do not lead to growth. High hygiene factors mean employees are not dissatisfied but not necessarily satisfied (Hassard and Cox, 2014). Growth needs help push towards self-realisation, comparable to Maslow's growth motives. Recognition for work leads to satisfaction but does not address avoidance needs, just as hygiene factors cannot satisfy growth needs (Whitsett and Winslow, 1967).

Both theories lack strong empirical support (Hassard and Cox, 2014). Maslow's theory overlooks individual cognitive processes, and Herzberg's methodology has been criticised. Mixed results in testing Herzberg's theory led to alternative theories, such as the Job Characteristics Model of Hackman and Oldham (1980).

Job Characteristics Model

According to the Job Characteristics Model of Hackman and Oldham (1980), five core job characteristics lead to high job satisfaction, intrinsic motivation, and positive performance outcomes: skill variety, autonomy, feedback, task identity, and task significance. The presence of job satisfaction is thought to have a reinforcing positive impact, acting as motivation for employees to persist in their assigned tasks, thereby contributing to organisational effectiveness (Ali et al., 2014). Several researchers supported the validity of the Job Characteristics Model highlighting its ability to measure the extent to which a job entails a number

of diverse skills and talents of the employee (Price and Muller, 1986; Ali et al., 2014). Task identity relates to the job's meaningfulness, motivating employees (Coelho and Augusto, 2010; Ali et al., 2014). Task significance measures the job's impact on others (Hackman and Oldham, 1980). One of the CAPS factors as well, autonomy provides employees with freedom and discretion in their work. Feedback offers information on performance effectiveness. Lastly, feedback is the measure of how performing the tasks mandated by the job provides the employee with information about the effectiveness of their performance. The study of Ali et al. (2014) examined the relationship between job characteristics and job satisfaction. Their results showed that all characteristics contributed the most to job satisfaction. This means that possible changes, such as implementing advanced technology solutions, to these five characteristics might change the job satisfaction of employees.

Job Satisfaction and Advanced Technologies

The implementation of advanced technologies (robots, artificial intelligence, automation) was considered a black box not fully understood (Bhargava, Bester and Bolton, 2021). Humans and AI need to work together, which is one of the CAPS factors. It is because technology and humans will complement one another, and employers should recruit or train employees with skills that complement the technologies (Plastino and Purdy, 2018). This can concern employees about the impact on their job satisfaction (Bhargava, Bester and Bolton, 2021). With advanced technologies taking on various tasks, employees' responsibilities will change, affecting their self-esteem and job satisfaction (Maslow, 1970). For instance, Findlay et al. (2017) found that implementing advanced technologies in pharmaceuticals increased patient contact but also led to fewer opportunities for role rotation, perceived splintering of teamwork, and limited career perspectives. Liu, Huang and Zhang (2018) showed that a smartphone-based gamified job design enhanced job satisfaction, motivation, and performance. Bhargava, Bester and Bolton (2021) found that the human touch and soft skills are irreplaceable by advanced technologies and that employees should see these technologies as opportunities, not threats. Employees are satisfied with the

advantages of implemented technologies, but are less satisfied with their social life, potential misuse of technology, and data theft. This shows that not all employees are satisfied with advanced technology in the workplace because the impact is subjective depending on employees' job role and seniority level. More specifically, low-skilled employees will have less possibilities of being reskilled or affording access to advanced technologies. This leads to social instability because of higher unemployment. Lastly, organisations need to be prepared for pre-and post-industrial change. All these findings are the main focus of our current research.

Job Satisfaction and AI

AI can complete the work of an employee easily (Kapur, 2022), such as using voice commands in the Google search engine, making work more efficient and impacting productivity, which in turn affects job satisfaction. Previous research showed that productivity and job satisfaction are correlated (Maslach and Leiter, 2008; Nicole et al., 2021; Sadeghian and Hassenzahl, 2022), which is a CAPS factor in our research. Another positive characteristic contributing to job satisfaction is job autonomy. In the study of Sadeghian and Hassenzahl (2022), participants indicated that autonomy is an important characteristic associated with positive feelings about collaboration with AI. To have positive collaborations between employees and AI, it is important to design the systems in order to fulfil the need for autonomy. automation and job satisfaction will affect employees in local labour markets (Schwabe and Castellacci, 2020). In particular, the low-skilled workers experience a significant risk of automation because they carry out routine-based tasks. Their work will be replaced by AI or other smart machines. Thus, it is very important to design advanced technologies tailored to the needs of the various employees in different industries, which is the main goal of the current research.

Interplay Between Workplace Safety and Job Satisfaction

One of the most important goals of organisations is to ensure the health and safety of employees, a basic need in Maslow's hierarchy (1970). Health and safety encompass physical, mental, and social well-being (Ratna and Kaur, 2016). Many industries face challenges related to safety and well-being due to quality control issues and work environment anomalies, leading to high stress levels.

Research shows a significant positive association between workplace safety and job satisfaction (Ayim Gyekye, 2005). Focusing on safety, well-being, and worker empowerment makes work more fulfilling (Breque, De Nul and Petridis, 2021). Workers with positive safety climate perceptions express more job satisfaction, exhibit more commitment to safety policies, and have fewer accidents (Smith, 2018). Conversely, negative safety perceptions, often due to high workload and job insecurity, lead to safety lapses and higher accident rates (Hofmann and Stetzer, 1996; Salminen, 1995).

The safety climate also includes psychological dimensions. Positive emotional responses to work experience and perceived well-being contribute to a positive safety climate, while dissatisfaction undermines safety efforts and increases accident risk (Ayim Gyekye, 2005). Despite recognising the impact of a positive safety climate on business outcomes, many leaders do not fully understand this relationship (Smith, 2018).

A safe workplace positively impacts productivity and performance. Absence of safety concerns creates a nurturing environment with better performance results. Comprehensive corporate wellness efforts reduce healthcare costs and absenteeism (Bunn et al., 2001). Safety training fosters a culture of safety and well-being, enhancing job satisfaction and motivation (Smith, 2018; Zacharatos, Barling and Iverson, 2005; Burke et al, 2006).

Advanced technologies may impact workplace safety. These technologies protect against diseases, injuries, and hazardous chemicals (Ratna and Kaur, 2016; Nazareno and Schiff, 2021). Ratna and Kaur (2016) found that advanced technologies improved injury and health conditions in tech companies. However,

Nazareno and Schiff (2021) found mixed results, with employees experiencing less stress but worse health. This underscores the importance of considering the type of work in studying safety.

The interplay between job satisfaction and safety stands as a crucial aspect for organisational success, efficacy and workers' well-being. Having a safe working environment helps employees shape their perception of their job and organisation. Thus, when implementing advanced technologies, employers and employees must work together and participate in health and safety programs for occupational health and safety practices to be successful. In this way, employees recognise their organisation values the safety and well-being of the employees, which in turn positively impacts job satisfaction (Ayim, 2005).

4.5 Conclusion

We started this section by asking what exactly these CAPS empowerment factors meant and why we chose to use these factors to apply in the workplace. Overall, the CAPS factors begin to tell a story of human-centred management of advanced technological solutions. Firstly, advanced technological solutions increasingly influence the way collaboration and creativity evolves in organisations. It is important to determine how employees can effectively collaborate with colleagues, stakeholders, and intelligent machines to ensure that work processes and outcomes meet the needs of both employees and organisations. An environment should be created that supports cross-functional collaboration and clearly communicates visions to foster innovative work (Hadjikosta and Friedrich, 2019). Secondly, to ensure more human-centric technology implementations, decisions about automation should also consider autonomy. By embracing principles of meaningful human control and prioritising greater autonomy, organisations can effectively navigate the complexities of automation. This approach empowers individuals, creates human-centric work environments, fosters creativity, and upholds human dignity in the face of technological advancements. Thirdly, with a human-centric focus to empower

workers, organisations would benefit from creating a good balance between privacy and productivity. Discussing productivity can introduce management's improvement plans and help employees understand the company's goals. However, managers typically have a strategic view of productivity, while assembly line operators have a more operational perspective (Tangen, 2005). This indicates that productivity must be understood differently at each level and that the methods for achieving high productivity may vary accordingly. Lastly, human-centric systems should aim to place human operator, their knowledge, and skills in key positions (Yi et al., 2024). By incorporating human-centred design principles, organisations can develop technology that aligns with workers' needs and behaviours, ultimately enhancing safety and usability (Wong et al., 2023).

Together, these CAPS empowerment factors begin to tell a story of human-centred management of technological solutions. Although these CAPS are organised separately for organisational purposes, as this project progresses, we will demonstrate the interconnected relationships between each CAPS factor. We argue that organisations operating at the intersections of these factors can become more human-centric. Enhancing collaboration in automation, production, and safety processes will foster greater creativity, autonomy, feelings of privacy, and job satisfaction.

5 Bibliometric Review

5.1 Objectives and scope of bibliometric research

The aim of the bibliometric research is to identify the main trends in the scientific journals, articles and literature that can be associated with the requirements of WP1 - Framework for Human-Centric Assessment. This bibliometric research meets the requirements of Task 1.1 (Benchmarking human-centric technology developments and transfer) and examines the practices, tendencies and emerging pathways in the relevant scientific literature and journals. This study clarifies conceptual issues on how to define human-centric tendencies and the dimensions of human-centrism in economic, organisational and industrial operational settings. Also, the bibliometric research helped us to identify the most relevant journals and scientific articles, which are mentioned in the specific sheets of each table in the following sections, new and emerging directions of research and areas of interests that should be considered when analysing human-centrism from the perspectives of the SEISMEC CAPS framework.

First, our research aims to identify and to describe the main clusters and areas that emerged from bibliometric research. Our research results in the identification of pathways and clear groups of trends based on keyword clusters in the scientific literature on the four CAPS tensions associated with human-centrism. These pathways and tendencies help us to understand the way in which the research in the field of economics, technology, organisations, social science and other relevant fields of science validate project approaches and correlations between CAPS tensions and human-centrism, pilot projects, and the three perspectives (employees, organisational and structural). We also emphasise the gaps between all CAPS elements in specific sections of bibliometric review. Our aim is to identify new clusters of keywords and trends that can be associated with CAPS tensions and human-centrism in the

specialised literature, to later validate them in the organisational contexts of the pilot projects within the project.

From the bibliometric research we have identified that a large part of the associations of the CAPS framework, as well as the associations between CAPS and human-centrism, validate new pathways in the direction of smart manufacturing, Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0. The clusters, reflected very clearly in the maps and links described in the following paragraphs, generate new directions and fields of research in organisations and technology. We will analyse these directions and concentrations of relevant key words.

After generating and identifying the main pathways from bibliometric research, we consider it useful to map themes and purpose of pilot projects with the findings of bibliometric research (clusters of words and pathways) to understand and to describe the links between SEISMEC pilot projects and pathways and clusters of keywords identified in bibliometric research. Based on the bibliometric research results and identified pathways, we generate a battery of criteria that characterise human-centrism based on CAPS tensions, SEISMEC pilot projects and preponderance of one of the three perspectives: employee, organisational and structural (structural means the links between technology and ethics, legal, social, environmental and cultural contexts).

5.2 Methodology and data collection

Bibliometrics represents a statistical method that is frequently used in academic literature reviews, which analyses the history of scientific works to measure impact. It entails using quantitative techniques, such as citation analysis on bibliometric data (which includes units of publication, citation, etc.) (Broadus, 1987), in order to understand the trends and evolutions of a particular field of study (Donthu, et al., 2021). Following Shi et al. (2022), we use a five-step methodology (data retrieval, data cleaning and formatting, data analysis, visualisation, and interpretation) to examine networks, evolutionary trends, and

the most influential elements (researchers, keywords, publications, etc.) in the field of human-centrism from a CAPS perspective: collaboration and creativity, autonomy and automation, privacy and productivity, safety and job satisfaction. In SEISMEC, the benefits of human centrism will be measured in Creativity, Collaboration, Autonomy, Automation, Productivity, Privacy, Safety and job Satisfaction, the CAPS empowerment factors for human-centrism. The SEISMEC shift introduces the CAPS empowerment factors and the associated tensions that shape the applications of human-centric solutions. Our work is linked with Task 1.2 which links the tensions to solution directions that make it possible to transcend these tensions. The following steps will be executed: (1) an existing list with possible solution primitives, with, for example, mutual human-AI learning extended with principles drawn from technology, psychology and organisation sciences; (2) the possible solution direction will be reviewed on their potential to transcend the identified tensions and their strengths and weaknesses, e.g., technology acceptance, algorithm aversion, and boundary work; (3) a final mapping with tensions and solution primitives will be established along with specific attention points. To validate fit of these solutions, one of the pilots is directly involved in the execution of this task. Demonstrating the SEISMEC shift requires not only a diverse set of pilots that can illustrate the feasibility of a human-centric industry in a wide range of contexts, but also an adequate framework for assessing the success of these pilots, especially in regard to the perspective of the workers that are at the core of this shift. As such, the CAPS empowerment factors that underpin the SEISMEC empowerment will be translated into outcomes which will be measured before and after SEISMEC's pilot interventions to assess the shift's success into a human-centric industry paradigm.

It is important to mention that bibliometric review as a method focuses solely on bibliometric data and does not entail a systematic literature review, but rather provides an overall image of the current state of knowledge in the field of human-centrism from CAPS framework perspective and organisational management, IT&C, social, economic and psychological standpoint. This research highlights the

connections between the keywords that are used by multiple researchers in various articles and provides an understanding of what has been studied and what are the gaps in research that need to be addressed. The bibliometric review is completed by a comprehensive and relevant literature review in the following chapter.

Articles, chapters and books relevant for this research (data) were gathered and organised from two renowned databases: Scopus and Web of Science. This choice is motivated by the fact that both (Scopus and Web of Science) are considered the biggest databases (Zhu & Liu, 2020), thus providing more data for our study, and by using both we can ensure a more comprehensive and diverse coverage of the literature relevant for our study. In addition, by using both databases we can cross-check our results and reduce the risk of missing important studies, which can occur if we rely solely on one database (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016).

In this research, a systematic search was conducted on the two databases described above, during April and May 2024. We used the Scopus and Web of Science databases, where we performed a search using the specific keywords (elements of CAPS framework):

Table 1 - Keywords associated to CAPS and searched in Scopus and Web of Science databases

Collaboration Creativity	Automation Autonomy	Productivity Privacy	Safety Job Satisfaction
Collaboration and human-centric	Autonomy and human-centric	Privacy and human-centric	Safety and human-centric
Creativity and human-centric	Automation and human-centric	Productivity and human-centric	Job satisfaction and human-centric
Creativity and collaboration	Autonomy and automation	Privacy and productivity	Safety and job satisfaction
Creativity and collaboration and human-centric	Autonomy and automation and human-centric	Privacy and productivity and human-centric	Safety and job satisfaction and human-centric

To increase the relevance of the retrieved articles, several inclusion criteria were applied, including the requirement that articles be peer-reviewed, given that these works constitute a body of verified knowledge and generally propose trustworthy findings (Tigre, et al., 2023), published in English, and related to analysed keywords associations. Additionally, only articles from the „subject areas” described in the following tables were included in the research covering, Social Sciences, Economics, Business, Management, Organisational Theories, Decision Science, Computer Science, Engineering and other relevant fields described in each table. The search was further refined by limiting the articles to those published after 2000 (included) in order to align with the subject matter of our research study, as well as with the dimensions of human-centricity in organisations. The choice of keywords for refining the search is motivated by the fact that in order to have a relevant dataset of papers related to human-centricity in relation with CAPS framework tensions we need to consider all the relevant dimensions and include them in our data retrieval step, otherwise we will have articles that do not fit the scope of this study and are therefore not relevant to be included in the analysis. Indeed, it is important to acknowledge that the use of those specific keywords for refining our search may inherently pose limitations, potentially leading to the oversight of pertinent articles that do not align with the predetermined keyword selection. Therefore, this limitation should be taken into consideration when interpreting the results.

5.3 Results

Data analysis represents the science mapping and co-word analysis. Science mapping involves categorising and visually representing the structure of a research area by grouping elements such as documents, authors, journals, and keywords. This process combines classification and visualisation techniques to create a graphical representation of the area’s organisation and structure. The techniques used for science mapping include citation analysis, co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, co-word analysis and co-authorship analysis, and by using these methods, we can gain valuable insights into the interconnections

between documents, authors, concepts, amongst others, in a certain field of study (Donthu, et al., 2021). We opted for science mapping, using co-word analysis to understand the research field by examining the interconnections between keywords to find the key contributors in the field, as well as prominent themes and emerging trends regarding human-centricity from CAPS methodology.

Visualisation of the science mapping techniques are needed in order to represent the classifications and networks that emerge (Župič & Čater, 2015). Thus, using a software specially created for network representation is necessary. For this, we used the VoSviewer software application to perform the network analysis as it works efficiently with different databases, in our case Web of Science and Scopus. Also, VoSviewer uses a clustering methodology that is useful in presenting the similarities between analysed objects (like co-word analysis) and it also provides accurate visual representations about the relations and the distance between any pair of objects (Waltman, et al., 2010). It is also one of the most popular software tool for creating maps based on network data and it is widely used amongst researchers (see Tigre et al., 2023; Shi, Mai, 2022; Chawla, Goyal, 2021). For example, in Figure 1 we can see the strongest links and clusters between the most relevant nodes represented by human-centric, automation, Industry 4.0 and 5.0. In this figure, we can see some new emerging fields represented by green and yellow clusters. This figure can be interpreted also as an evolution of concepts, new emerging fields of knowledge and validation of links between human-centrism and automation. These graphs are also relevant from the perspective of CAPS tensions validation. These associations are validated through the figures by relevant thematic clusters represented with different colours, strong links between clusters represented by keywords, and new emerging fields in scientific literature and research represented with green and yellow.

Figure 7 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between human-centrism and automation

In the following subsections we will present the most relevant thematic clusters resulting from bibliometric research. The information will be summarised in tables. Each CAPS tensions and the thematic clusters resulting from the bibliometric research are presented in separate tables. Each table includes the most relevant resulting thematic clusters, emerging new fields of knowledge, the strongest links between clusters, correlations with the SEISMEC Pilots and the perspective that can be associated with these keyword clusters. The tables are based on figures and bibliometric research for each CAPS tensions, and are validated by scientific literature and research, thematic clusters and strong links generated by VOS Viewer. For each CAPS tension we added human-centric to understand and to analyse if there are specific connections and particularities between them and human centrism.

In the Appendix section, more information is presented related to how the keywords were searched in the Web of Science and SCOPUS databases, journals, the number of articles identified, as well as the graphs showing the thematic clusters of words.

5.3.1 Collaboration, Creativity and Human-Centricity

Table 2 - Clusters discovered in scientific literature associated with pilots and perspectives

Collaboration, Creativity and Human-Centric		
Relevant keywords clusters	Correlations with pilots	Perspective
human-robot collaboration, intelligent robots, human-machine, creativity, problem solving, engineering education, creative self-efficacy, affect and creativity, multi-disciplinary education, context aware, collaborative working	Focus #1 Work Organisation Focus #2 Skills & Training	Employees
smart manufacturing, Industry 5.0, Industry 4.0, cyber-physical systems, sustainable development, learning systems, design for future, cognitive digital twin, enterprise architecture, distributed knowledge, service-oriented architecture, collaborative systems and services, cognitive systems	Focus #4 Management & Governance Focus #5 Business Models Focus #7 Tasks & Functions	Organisational
artificial intelligence, robots, internet of things, social aspects, flexible support, cobots, computational intelligence	Focus #6 Corporate Values & Ethics	Structural
<p>As we can see in the Figure nr. 8 which investigates the links between collaboration and human-centric the main tendencies and pathways in the scientific literature is to form clusters around: artificial intelligence, human-robot collaboration, Industry 5.0, deep learning, smart manufacturing, cyber-physical systems, human-robot interaction and collaboration.</p> <p>The latest research in collaboration and creativity in relation with human-centrism are mainly in the field of Industry 5.0, digital twin, human-centric smart manufacturing, digital transformation, metaverse, edge computing, blockchain, wellbeing, mixed reality, human-cyber-physical systems, ergonomics, optimisation.</p> <p>In Figure nr. 9 one of the most relevant clusters based on creativity and human-centrism strongest links are around problem solving and decision making, creativity and artificial intelligence and Industry 5.0. There is a new emerging field that link artificial intelligence with human-centrism in problem solving, digital twin in organisations and innovation.</p>		

Based on the Figure nr. 4 we tried to analyse if there are some emerging fields based on strongest links between collaboration and creativity. We saw that there are strong clusters of keywords around human-computer interaction, artificial intelligence, product design, co-design, virtual reality, education, computer aided instruction, innovation and learning. The new and emerging pathways are around these topics.

In Figure nr. 10 some key clusters and trends are presented for the association between collaboration, creativity and human-centricity. The co-occurrences between these three elements are not so strong because the numbers of articles found in the scientific literature is not very high, more precisely only 35 articles were included. There are strong linkages between organisational elements like context aware, distributed knowledge, service-oriented architecture, decision-making, collaborative working and collaboration systems and services and human machine interaction, digital transformation, artificial intelligence and Industry 5.0. The tendencies and pathways are concentrated around organisational prerequisites and contexts, virtual reality, Industry 5.0, human-robot collaboration and computational intelligence.

Figure 8 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between collaboration and human-centric

Figure 9 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between creativity and human-centric

Figure 10 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between collaboration and human-centric

Figure 11 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between collaboration, creativity and human-centric

5.3.2 Autonomy, Automation and Human-centricity

Table 3 - Clusters discovered in scientific literature associated with pilots and perspectives

Autonomy, Automation and Human-Centric		
Relevant keywords clusters	Correlations with pilots	Perspective
man-machines systems, autonomy, behavioural forecasting, level of autonomies, cognitive workload, human engineering, human-centric systems, adjustable autonomy, behavioural research, operator 4.0, human-robot collaboration, problem solving, safety, trust	Focus #1 Work Organisation Focus #2 Skills & Training Focus #7 Tasks & Functions	Employees
Industry 5.0, Industry 4.0, digital transformation, smart spaces, cyber-physical systems, autonomous manufacturing, accident preventions, energy efficiency, risk management, data analytics, smart environments, intelligent buildings, ergonomics, data integration, process control, optimisation, levels of automation, decision making	Focus #3 Health & Safety Focus #4 Management & Governance Focus #5 Business Models	Organisational
sustainable development, Society 5.0, supply chains, artificial intelligence methods, ethical principles, human-centric design, digital twin, environmental humanity, robots, mixed reality, autonomous agents, intelligent agents, human robots, multi-agent systems, autonomous systems, blockchain, ubiquitous computing, big data, sustainability, circular economy, supply chains, economic and social effects, automated systems, cognitive systems, automated surveillance	Focus #6 Corporate Values & Ethics	Structural

As we can see in the Figure nr. 12 there is a clustering around certain keywords specific to organisations and employees, and the trend in scientific articles highlights the emergence of new fields such as behavioural forecasting, accident prevention, task allocation, artificial intelligence and autonomous manufacturing. In their vast majority, these articles have as a common point the

concept of Industry 5.0 and decision-making processes in organisations, as well as the degree of decision-making autonomy.

Automation and human-centric co-occurrences was based on a larger number of articles, exactly 300. We identified a number of key clusters and strong links between them, namely automation, intelligent buildings, Internet of Things, cyber-physical systems, decision making, Industry 5.0, behavioural research, man-machine systems, embedded systems and others reflected in the images. Human-centric is strongly linked, in articles where automation is present, with new pathways defined by Industry 4.0, Industry 5.0, digital transformation, factory automation, virtual reality, ergonomics, human-centric design, automated systems, pattern and activity recognition and optimisation algorithms.

Analysing the links between automation and autonomy there is a high degree of connectivity from which five major thematic clusters emerge around the two concepts. The first cluster with a significant variety of keywords is concentrated around digitised organisations, autonomous systems and factory automation. The second cluster is organised around artificial intelligence and decision-making with a strong link to the autonomy keyword, and the third cluster is about human resources and their integration into automated processes. The fifth thematic cluster introduces concepts of robots and human-robot interaction. The main tendencies and pathways from old to new is from robotics to artificial intelligence and autonomy with strong links between these elements and human conditions in organisations.

The links between autonomy, automation and human-centricity could not be assessed and analysed because in literature we found only three articles with co-occurrences between these keywords. There are some gaps that can be analysed and described.

Figure 12 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between autonomy and human-centric

Figure 13 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between automation and human-centric

Figure 14 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between autonomy and automation

For the triptych autonomy AND automation AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links only 5 articles were found. This means that there are gaps in the scientific literature between the three concepts.

5.3.3 Privacy, Productivity and Human-Centricity

Table 4 - Clusters discovered in scientific literature associated with pilots and perspectives

Privacy, Productivity and Human-Centric		
Relevant keywords clusters	Correlations with pilots	Perspective
privacy, behavioural research, human-computer interaction, human-centric computing, human-centric AI, human-robot collaboration, occupational risks, productivity enhancement, human-in-the-loop, human-centric design, wellbeing, digital humans, human-centric, digital human simulation, productivity, assistance systems, human-centric lighting, behavioural research, accident prevention, ergonomics, job satisfaction, access control	Focus #1 Work Organisation Focus #2 Skills & Training Focus #3 Health & Safety Focus #4 Management & Governance	Employees
data driven, security of data, transparency, information management, knowledge management, smart factory, human resource management, production systems, automation, cost effectiveness, efficiency,	Focus #4 Management & Governance Focus #5 Business Models Focus #7 Tasks & Functions	Organisational
metaverse, privacy-preserving techniques, ethics, learning systems, machine-learning, cybersecurity, blockchain, privacy and security, deep learning, artificial intelligence, ubiquitous computing, laws and legislation, data privacy, Industry 5.0, economic and social effects, safety, ethical technology, sustainable	Focus #6 Corporate Values & Ethics	Structural

Figure 16 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between productivity and human-centric

Figure 17 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between privacy and productivity

For the triptych privacy AND productivity AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links only 7 articles were found. This means that there are gaps in the scientific literature between the three concepts.

5.3.4 Safety, Job Satisfaction and Human-Centricity

Table 5 - Clusters discovered in scientific literature associated with pilots and perspectives

Safety, Job Satisfaction and Human-Centric		
Relevant keywords clusters	Correlations with pilots	Perspective
human-robot integration, human engineering, human factors, human-robot interaction and collaboration, man-machine systems, motion planning, resilience, occupational risks, behavioural research, wellbeing, human-centric design, health, operator 4.0, generations, behaviour assessment, privacy, cooperative behaviour, psychological wellbeing, motivation, satisfaction, education, workload, occupational safety, burnout, ergonomics, job stress, risk assessment, social support, mental health	Focus #1 Work Organisation Focus #2 Skills & Training Focus #3 Health & Safety	Employees
man-machine systems, ergonomics, optimisations, security systems, smart manufacturing, learning systems, performance, decision making, life cycle, business process management, job demands-resource model, behavioral operation management, leadership, personnel management, organisational culture, team work, safety management, accident prevention,	Focus #4 Management & Governance Focus #7 Tasks & Functions	Organisational
machine design, intelligent robots, Industry 5.0, safety engineering, safety, embedded systems, artificial intelligence, virtual reality, digital twin, automation	Focus #6 Corporate Values & Ethics	Structural
Starting from the fourth CAPS tension we analysed the relationship between safety, job satisfaction and human-centricity. In the relationship between		

safety and human-centricity in Figure nr. 18, we identified four major clusters around the following keywords: safety engineering, Industry 5.0, decision making & behavioural research, human-robot integration. The main tendencies and pathways are from man-machine systems, embedded systems intelligent systems and robots to the integration of collaborative robots, human-robot collaboration, security, resilience, artificial intelligence, performance, wellbeing, virtual reality and risk assessment in human-centric activities. One important aspect here is the strong link between behavioural research and relevant clusters, and the new tendency to integrate digital technologies in work activities.

In Figure nr. 19 the occurrences and strongest links between job satisfaction and human-centrism are presented. In this case, we identified three key clusters, namely job satisfaction, workplace and robotics, but there are no significant links between them. Each of these clusters is connected with other relevant keywords, especially words that define the job-satisfaction. The main trend is to integrate digital technologies in checking human behaviour, job satisfaction, behaviour and wellbeing.

The links between safety and job satisfaction are presented in Figure nr. 20. From this perspective, we have identified four dominant clusters, more precisely aspects that are related to personnel management and leadership, factors associated with workplace like burnout and well-being, and other clusters associated with safety, occupational risks, accident preventions and ergonomics.

Figure 18 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between safety and human-centric

Figure 19 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between job-satisfaction and human-centric

Figure 20 - Relevant clusters, emerging fields of knowledge and strong links between safety and job-satisfaction

For the triptych safety AND job satisfaction AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links only 3 articles were found. This means that there are gaps in the scientific literature between the three concepts.

6 Instrumentalising CAPS to calibrate human-centrism in the workplace

The theoretical and empirical overviews with relation to human-centrism serve as an important starting point for human-centrism, given that they provide a solid foundation for the SEISMEC pilots. Nevertheless, the main challenge that SEISMEC has embarked upon is to materialise the concept of “human-centrism” with the help of practical tools. In this sense, the aim of this section is to instrumentalise the main concepts of the deliverable into a benchmark of analysis that can be used to assess the orientation towards human-centrism. Benchmarking will take place based on the 4 complementary factors that form the core of SEISMEC.

The purpose of the benchmark is to provide a starting point for the assessment of human-centric practices in the workplace. The way in which the benchmark works is that it provides a series of questions of self-reflection and assessment with regards to the human-centric quality of the practices, tools, procedures, activities, structures, and relations in which social partners engage. Due to the socio-technical view that the project takes, as well as the results of the theoretical and empirical research, the benchmark is multi-levelled. It has three levels of analysis: the employee, the organisation, and the industry level. They are all intertwined and interdependent. At **employee level**, we aim to assess the perceptions and experiences of employees with regards to human-centric practices in the workplace. At organisational level, we aim to invite self-reflection and assessment of the multitude of practices, tools, procedures, and activities that the originate at management level. At industry level, we aim to help gauge the practices of the entire industrial ecosystem. For each level, there are various possibilities of respondents, but they each feed back to that particular level. Questions related to employees should be answered by employees and/or their representatives at the level of the workplace. Organisational questions should be answered by the management level, while the questions related to the industry

should be answered at the level of industry associations or at the management level that deals with the connection with the industry (business organisations, for instance).

However, several limitations may arise. At this point, the benchmark is a qualitative analysis and takes the form of open-ended questions. This invites self-reflection on the part of the employees, organisations, and at industry level, aiming to gauge their integration of human-centric principles and practices. We assume that the benchmark is an iterative exercise, and it will be improved, transformed into a quantitative analysis with scales and metrics, based on a first exercise with the pilots. Table 1 details the benchmarking questions. Table 2 provides a series of examples of Likert scale questions that can be used in the second iteration of the benchmarking exercise.

Table 6 - Human-centric benchmarking

	Collaboration	Creativity
Employee	<p>What type of collaborative tools and technologies do you use?</p> <p>How did you learn about the collaborative potential of new technologies?</p> <p>Has there been any on-boarding in relation to the collaborative potential of the new technologies?</p> <p>What degree of collaborative work between humans and technologies (e.g. integration of human and artificial intelligence) exists in the tasks, activities and processes?</p>	<p>Have there been any employee innovative ideas that have been launched and supported at company level?</p> <p>If yes, how many in a given period?</p>
Organisation	<p>What type of collaborative technologies does the organisation provide?</p> <p>Has the organisation performed any consultations</p>	<p>Does the employee job description (and/or other mandatory personnel files) detail the possibility for creative development of new</p>

	<p>with the employees prior/during the development, implementation of new technologies?</p> <p>How was the feedback collected?</p> <p>Are there rewards foreseen in the job description to incentivise collaboration in the implementation of advanced technologies?</p>	<p>tools, processes, and/or tasks with the use of technologies?</p> <p>Does your organisation provide employees with opportunities to co-design new technology tools and their respective processes?</p> <p>How does your organisation reward employees for their creative initiatives in the use of technology tools?</p>
<p>Industry</p>	<p>Are there any industry groups that discuss and create frameworks for collaboration within that industry?</p> <p>Are there any consultations with relevant stakeholders (trade unions, NGOs etc)</p> <p>How often do these consultations take place?</p>	<p>Is there an industry standard for boosting creativity in the workplace?</p> <p>Are there any co-learning opportunities for industry organisations?</p>

	Autonomy	Automation
<p>Employee</p>	<p>Can you decide for yourselves in terms of tasks, processes, respecting organisational boundaries and agreements?</p> <p>What types of decision-making are employees allowed to perform in terms of technology use?</p>	<p>Do you choose and/or evaluate the integration of automation in their daily tasks?</p> <p>Does the automation of daily tasks contribute to an increase in perceived well-being? Does job scheduling play a role here?</p>
<p>Organisation</p>	<p>In the use of technology, are there any company policies implemented to support employee autonomy, especially as regards AI?</p>	<p>What percentage of tasks, processes, procedures are fully automated in your organisation? Is there a</p>

	<p>Are the policies changed/updated along with the update of technologies?</p> <p>Are there any structures developed in the organisation to monitor the implementation of such policies?</p>	<p>mixed model of production developed?</p> <p>How does the organisation decide on the automation potential of procedures and tasks? (alternatively - what factors contribute to the automation of certain tasks?)</p> <p>Who decides and implements automation procedures?</p>
<p>Industry</p>	<p>Are there any industry standards and/or agreements that help enable employee autonomy?</p> <p>Is there a dialogue in place with relevant social partners as regards employee autonomy</p>	<p>Does automation improve industry performance?</p> <p>Does the industry measure the potential for well-being of automation?</p> <p>Does the increase in efficiency translate into the well-being of workers?</p>

	Privacy	Productivity
<p>Employee</p>	<p>Are you actively informed about the use of your data for organisational purposes?</p> <p>How are you informed about the use of your data?</p> <p>Do you have adequate avenues to report on misuses of personal data?</p>	<p>How do you perceive the role of technologies in your overall productivity?</p> <p>How do you report on your activity when engaged in flexible working arrangements?</p> <p>How do you balance the use of technology and flexible working arrangements in the search of productivity?</p>
<p>Organisation</p>	<p>What data protection policies are in place in the organisation?</p>	<p>What frameworks for monitoring employee productivity does the organisation have?</p>

	<p>Does your organisation have a DPO? (for organisations for which a DPO is not mandatory)</p> <p>Are there any regular trainings/informative sessions on personal data protection?</p>	<p>Does the organisation put in place mechanisms in order to balance productivity optimisation and ethical challenges?</p> <p>Describe the mechanisms.</p>
<p>Industry</p>	<p>What is the level of regulatory compliance in terms of protection of personal data at industry level? Have there been any significant data breaches?</p> <p>Does the industry have a framework in place to safeguard personal data/reduce privacy concerns?</p>	<p>How does the industry balance the search for productivity and the attention to human-centric objectives? What choices has the industry made in this sense?</p>

	Safety	Satisfaction
<p>Employee</p>	<p>Do you perceive the workplace as a safe (physically and mentally) place to work?</p> <p>How do you report and address safety risks?</p> <p>Are you empowered to identify and propose solutions to safety risks?</p> <p>What frameworks do you have at their disposal?</p>	<p>Do you have a framework to report on their job satisfaction? Is it periodical?</p> <p>How do you report on your job satisfaction? Are there any technologies involved in this measurement and monitoring?</p> <p>What tools and resources do you use to improve the perceived level of job satisfaction?</p>
<p>Organisation</p>	<p>Does the organisation foster a safe environment, especially as regards the use of new/untested technologies?</p>	<p>Are the indicators of job satisfaction aggregated at an organisational/ a departmental level?</p>

	<p>How does the organisation ensure such a safe environment?</p> <p>Is there a cybersecurity culture developed within the organisation?</p>	<p>Are there any technologies involved in this measurement and monitoring?</p> <p>What tools and processes enable the increase of job satisfaction?</p>
Industry	<p>What safety standards have there been developed across the industry?</p> <p>How does the industry as a whole approach cybersecurity?</p> <p>Is AI safety a priority at an industry level?</p>	<p>Is job satisfaction an active discussion point across the industry (from the best of your knowledge)?</p> <p>What role does technology play in the pursuit of job satisfaction across the industry?</p> <p>What measures have been taken to increase overall job satisfaction across the industrial sector?</p>

Table 7 – Likert scale based CAPS questions

Collaboration	Creativity
<p>What is the degree of collaboration between humans and digital systems (robots, machines, digital tools) within your organisation.</p> <p>Answers: from 1-5 (1 - no collaboration, 5 - high degree of collaboration)</p>	<p>Organisational results, performance, efficiency and productivity are influenced by the relation between human - centrist / affect and creativity.</p> <p>Answers: from 1-5 (1 – to a very little extent, 5- to a very large extent)</p>
Autonomy	Automation
<p>What is the degree of human autonomy based on human - machine interaction.</p>	<p>Human safety, trust, workload and behaviour are taken into consideration in automating tasks and activities within your organisation.</p>

Answers: from 1-5 (1 - no autonomy, 5 - high degree of autonomy)

Answers: from 1-5 (1 – to a very little extent, 5- to a very large extent)

Privacy	Productivity
<p>Occupational risks are taken into consideration in human-centric computing, human-machine interaction and collaboration and integration of AI in human work processes.</p> <p>Answers: from 1-5 (1 – to a very little extent, 5- to a very large extent)</p>	<p>Data-driven approaches are implemented to enhance productivity and privacy.</p> <p>Answers: from 1-5 (1 – to a very little extent, 5- to a very large extent)</p>

Safety	Satisfaction
<p>Safety and job satisfaction are based on human factors, and human-machine behaviour research.</p> <p>Answers: from 1-5 (1 – to a very little extent, 5- to a very large extent)</p>	<p>Integration of digital systems, digital tools, machines and robots in organisational structural systems are enhancing the safety and job satisfaction.</p> <p>Answers: from 1-5 (1 – to a very little extent, 5- to a very large extent)</p>

6.1 Conclusion

The main purpose of Deliverable 1.1 has been to begin the operationalisation of human-centrism as a concept, starting from the assumption that CAPS factors help materialise the human-centred management of advanced technological solutions. We pursued this purpose from three main angles. First, the extensive literature overview created a baseline of the connections between CAPS themselves and CAPS and human-centrism to confirm the connections between them. The second step was an empirical analysis that looked into existing practices and conceptualisations of human-centrism stemming from previous and on-going European-funded projects. Finally, a literature review defined the CAPS factors *per se* to establish coherence.

In order to help start a measurement on how human-centric an organisation can be, the final step of this deliverable was the design of a set of questions to invite self-reflection and assessment of human-centric organisations. The process of benchmarking is an iterative one. At this point, as the section on CAPS established, the factors are separated, but the aim is to apply, test, and re-apply the benchmarking in order to refine it and to establish the congruence between collaboration and creativity, between autonomy and automation, privacy and productivity, and safety and job satisfaction.

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8 Appendix A

8.1 Collaboration AND Creativity co-occurrences and strongest links (SCOPUS Elsevier and Web of Science)

8.1.1 Collaboration AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

Create Map X

Verify selected keywords

Selected	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-centric	90	508
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-robot collaboration	52	347
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 5.0	29	199
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	robots	24	153
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 4.0	22	147
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	smart manufacturing	16	145
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	intelligent robots	16	136
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human robot interaction	17	129
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	embedded systems	12	127
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	decision making	18	126
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	artificial intelligence	24	117
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collaboration	21	102
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-robot collaboration	12	100
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	virtual reality	16	99
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	deep learning	12	95
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cyber-physical systems	7	87
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	flow control	7	81
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cyber physical system	8	80
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-machine	8	80

8.1.2 Creativity AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

Create Map ✕

Verify selected keywords

Selected	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-centric	10	36
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	artificial intelligence	8	21
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	creativity	9	19
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	problem solving	4	18
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	internet of things	5	17
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	engineering education	4	14
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	digital storage	4	12
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 5.0	7	12
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	technology	3	12
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	decision making	3	11
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	virtual reality	2	11
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	design	3	9
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	learning systems	2	9
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	robotics	2	9
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	computer software	2	8
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	distributed computer systems	2	8
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	social aspects	2	8
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	artificial intelligence technologies	2	7
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	decision-making process	2	7

8.1.3 Collaboration AND creativity co-occurrences and strongest links

8.1.4 Collaboration AND creativity AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

8.2 Autonomy AND Automation co-occurrences and strongest links (SCOPUS Elsevier and Web of Science)

8.2.1 Autonomy AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

Create Map ✕

Verify selected keywords

Selected	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-centric	20	304
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	artificial intelligence	8	110
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	decision making	5	93
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	robots	5	84
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	autonomy	7	78
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human robot interaction	4	71
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 5.0	6	71
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	man machine systems	4	71
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	robotics	4	68
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	embedded systems	3	64
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	virtual reality	3	60
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	energy efficiency	3	56
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-robot collaboration	3	56
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cyber physical system	3	55
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 4.0	4	52
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	automation	3	51
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	design	3	49
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	risk assessment	2	47
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	intelligent robots	2	43

8.2.2 Automation AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

8.2.3 Autonomy AND automation co-occurrences and strongest links

8.3 Privacy AND Productivity co-occurrences and strongest links (SCOPUS Elsevier and Web of Science)

8.3.1 Privacy AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

8.3.2 Productivity AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

8.3.3 Privacy AND Productivity co-occurrences and strongest links

Create Map X

 Verify selected keywords

Selected	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	data privacy	165	686
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	privacy	128	537
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	internet of things	109	529
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	productivity	128	463
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	security	71	370
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	network security	56	298
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	artificial intelligence	69	246
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cloud computing	57	243
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	security of data	51	230
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	blockchain	49	218
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cryptography	43	202
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	security and privacy	49	201
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	machine learning	40	197
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human	40	189
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	digital storage	30	180
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	decision making	39	169
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	authentication	33	167
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	block-chain	24	158
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	information management	30	154

8.4 Safety AND Job satisfaction co-occurrences and strongest links (SCOPUS Elsevier and Web of Science)

7.4.1 Safety AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

Create Map X

Verify selected keywords

Selected	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-centric	68	222
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	accident prevention	31	136
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 4.0	22	91
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	decision making	22	88
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	behavioral research	19	82
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human robot interaction	15	81
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 5.0	22	79
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	workers'	14	75
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	safety	15	72
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-robot collaboration	14	63
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reinforcement learning	9	60
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	safety engineering	21	60
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	manufacture	10	56
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	vehicles	11	56
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ergonomics	11	53
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	occupational risks	10	50
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	virtual reality	11	49
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	artificial intelligence	15	47
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	motion planning	8	45

7.4.2 Job satisfaction AND human-centric co-occurrences and strongest links

Create Map X

Verify selected keywords

Selected	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	job satisfaction	3	44
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	job analysis	2	39
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	optimization	2	39
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	task analysis	2	39
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	industry 5.0	2	38
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human-centric	2	36
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	workplace	2	36
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	health care	2	29
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	robotics	2	28
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	article	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	behavior assessment	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	biodiversity	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cluster analysis	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	data aggregation	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	decomposition	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	england	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	human	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	humans	1	24
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	indoor environment	1	24

7.4.3 Safety AND Job satisfaction co-occurrences and strongest links

